
Turing Technical Report

Machine translation quality estimation
literature review

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1 Executive Summary

Machine translation (MT) systems enable the automated translation of text from a [source](#) to a [target](#) language. Even though the performance of MT systems has improved significantly in recent years they are not immune to errors. Errors that alter the meaning of a translation may be rare, but they remain [critical](#). Additionally, increased fluency of MT output might make it harder to identify errors. This motivates the requirement to assess the quality of translations, particularly in use cases where the impact of an incorrect translation can be significant.

Quality estimation (QE) predicts the quality of a translation given only the source language text and the target machine-translated text. QE is usually carried out at either [word-level](#), predicting a binary ‘OK’ or ‘BAD’ tag for each word in the translated text, or at [sentence-level](#), predicting a single score that represents the overall quality of the translated sentence. The attraction of QE is that it can be conducted at run-time without the need for a gold-standard [reference](#) translation.

The task is immediately challenging as defining translation quality can be subjective and requires weighing several dimensions against each other, such as fluency, style and accuracy. Additionally, error severity is likely use case dependent. If an application of MT is to communicate on a professional level with customers or clients, then stylistic or minor grammatical errors might be considered major, even when they do not affect the meaning of the text. Quality scores can also differ between individual annotators given the same annotation guidelines, even when using professional translators and linguists. It is common practice to use protocols for reaching annotator consensus and to derive a single ground-truth score.

The majority of [state-of-the-art \(SOTA\)](#) QE systems are ensembles of models that fine-tune an encoder-only [pre-trained language model \(PLM\)](#) with QE data. These models treat the MT system as a [black-box](#) as they do not require any information from the MT model, other than the output translation. In the last year, there have also been some QE systems that use a decoder-only [large language model \(LLM\)](#) to make predictions from prompts. This approach is not dominant but may

attract more attention in future years as it has the advantage of not requiring large amounts of training data.

The performance of QE systems is typically measured using correlation between the predictions and the ground-truth scores on a test set. The performance of SOTA QE models can produce relatively high correlations for some language pairs, even with little or no training data. In recent years, [fine-tuned QE models](#) have found performance gains by scaling up the size of the PLM used as a base model although the trade-off between size and performance is not clear. As the amount of data available for training such models is limited, many approaches also find additional performance by augmenting the existing datasets with synthetic data, in particular, to represent more records that contain [critical errors](#), which alter the meaning of the original text.

Alternative formulations of the QE task exist from predicting a binary sentence-level label (indicating the presence of a critical error) to producing explainable output, identifying error spans with severity labels in the text. Such formulations may be capable of producing more user-friendly outputs than a single score. Uncertainty quantification methods can also be used to output an uncertainty score or confidence interval with the prediction. All of these tasks remain fairly underdeveloped compared to the core QE task.

In conclusion, QE can produce relatively high correlations with ground truth scores in many situations. However, high performance is not guaranteed across all tasks and language-pairs and there are many considerations that are relevant to deploying a QE system in a real-world scenario. Test data needs to accurately reflect the task at hand and sufficiently represent the language pairs and text domains of interest. Additionally, it needs to be annotated with the specific use case in mind, following the appropriate definition of quality and providing the required granularity of output.

2 Introduction

[MT](#) systems enable the automated translation of text from a [source](#) to a [target](#) language, which can be beneficial for many businesses and organisations. However, MT systems are not immune to errors and there is additional concern that the increased fluency and comprehensibility of MT output might make it harder to spot errors ([Popović, 2020](#)). When MT systems are applied to critical use cases the translations are likely to be checked by a human linguist.

[QE](#) is the task of predicting the quality of a translation using a machine learning model given only the source and translated text ([Specia et al., 2010](#)). As QE systems make predictions without access to a [reference](#) text, such as a gold-standard human translation, the task is also referred to as [reference-free evaluation](#) ([Zhao et al., 2020](#)). QE systems have the potential to act as a decision making aid. One use case for QE given in the literature is to prioritise translations for [post-editing](#) by a linguist ([Cambra and Nunziatini, 2022](#)). Additionally, the ability to evaluate or rank MT systems without the need for human-translated reference sentences could result in a reduced cost and time for the evaluation process.

This report provides a literature review of recent developments in QE. Throughout this report, a knowledge of modern language modelling approaches, including the [transformers](#) architecture, commonly used [PLMs](#) (e.g., encoders such as [BERT](#)) and [LLMs](#) is assumed. The annual [Conference on Machine Translation \(WMT\)](#)¹ is the main venue for MT and QE research and is the main reference for [SOTA](#) results throughout.²

[Section 3](#) provides a brief overview of MT challenges and considers specific situations where they are vulnerable to generating low-quality translations. This is followed by an overview of approaches

¹The conference was originally called the Workshop on Statistical Machine Translation, hence WMT.

²There is also the international conference on spoken language translation (IWSLT) and regional conferences such as the Workshop on Asian Translation (WAT) or Conference of the European Association of Machine Translation (EAMT).

to measuring MT quality in [Section 4](#) and the available datasets used for training and testing QE systems in [Section 5](#). A review of QE methods is then presented in [Section 6](#), with a focus on recent trends and models. The performance of SOTA QE systems is presented in [Section 7](#), drawing on results from WMT 2023.

The typical approach to QE is to generate a single statistic that predicts the quality of the translation either at the [word-level](#) or [sentence-level](#). [Section 8](#) considers alternative QE tasks. This might be flagging sentences that contain critical errors in their translations, or identifying word-spans in sentences that have not been translated correctly as a means of explaining the overall sentence-level quality score. [Section 9](#) also considers methods that extend QE beyond a point prediction and presents approaches that quantify uncertainty of predictions. [Section 10](#) summarises the reviewed literature and discusses some practical considerations for implementing QE systems.

3 Machine Translation (MT) Challenges

3.1 Overview

MT models are trained to translate [source](#) language text into a [target](#) language. A model can be trained for a single language pair or for translations between multiple languages (so-called multilingual MT models). The SOTA in MT are [transformer](#)-based encoder-decoder models trained specifically for translation ([Vaswani et al., 2017](#); [Kocmi et al., 2023](#)), but there is also emerging work on the potential use of more general decoder-only LLMs for the task ([Kocmi et al., 2023](#)). Even though MT quality has improved significantly in recent years ([Macketanz et al., 2022](#)), it remains a challenging task.

The available MT training data are more representative of some language pairs, such as English-German, and of some domains, especially structured technical texts, such as news content or official and legal documents. This can impact translation quality for the less well represented language pairs and domains.

This section gives an overview of some of the features that make MT challenging. Specifically, it describes limitations of the available training data and the types of translation errors that might arise. For instance, [user-generated content \(UGC\)](#), such as social media posts or reviews is often noisy and makes uses of slang and idioms. These features can contribute to the translation containing [critical errors](#) whereby the translation significantly alters or even completely reverses the intended meaning of the source text.

3.2 Data Challenges

The primary data sources for MT research are parallel corpora, which contain translations of the same document in one or more languages.³ Parallel corpora can be created:

- **Manually:** human translating the [source](#) text or [post-editing](#) machine translated text
- **Automatically:** crawling the web for multilingual texts
- **Synthetically:** [back-translating](#) text in the [target](#) language into the source language using another MT system, usually one that is smaller and cheaper, thus creating a source-target translation pair while ensuring the target remains of high quality⁴

³Best practice for parallel data curation is an ongoing area of research and remains a subtask at WMT ([Sloto et al., 2023](#)).

⁴Translated text can exhibit characteristics that differentiate it from text originally written in a given language and

It is common to distinguish between **low-resource** and **high-resource** language pairs based on the amount of parallel corpora that exist. The terms do not have an exact definition but there are some language pairs that are generally agreed to fall into either of these categories. Translations from English into German, Chinese or Russian are common examples of high-resource language pairs, whereas translations from English into Marathi or Gujarati are considered low-resource language pairs (Tang et al., 2020; Blain et al., 2023).

While resource availability has an impact on MT quality there might be other factors that make particular language pairs easier to translate than others. For example, in one of the key datasets consisting of machine translated text accompanied by human quality scores on a scale of 0–100, English-German and English-Chinese, both high-resource language pairs, have an average score of 82.61 and 62.86 respectively (Fomicheva et al., 2022). Popović et al. (2020) observed that discrepancy in MT quality scores could be a result of lower quality, rather than quantity, of training data. They additionally suggested some languages might be inherently more difficult to translate (e.g., languages that possess grammatical gender or cases). Contrary to what one might assume, translation between closely related languages from the same language family (e.g., Spanish-Catalan or Spanish-Portuguese) also varies in quality by language pair and domain (Akhbardeh et al., 2021).

Parallel corpora are also more representative of some domains than others. For example, they are regularly created in official contexts with structured texts such as documents and speeches from the UN and EU institutions. Domain representation can be somewhat addressed by creating synthetic examples from monolingual data but the synthetic examples have to be balanced with the amount of genuine parallel data (Stahlberg, 2019).

As a result, **domain generalisation** has been gaining attention in MT research. This has been reflected in the main WMT task, which has historically been defined as news translation with other domain specific translations tackled as separate sub-tasks (e.g., biomedical or literary translation). In recent years, WMT have expanded their test data for the main translation task from just news content to also include e-commerce, social and conversational data (Kocmi et al., 2022, 2023).⁵

A particularly challenging text domain is noisy, informal or non-standard input (Li et al., 2019). This is a common characteristic of **UGC**, such as product reviews or social media posts. Examples include spelling mistakes, grammatical errors, non-standard spelling, such as “wanna” instead of “want to”, or hashtags. UGC is also more likely to contain slang, dialects and idioms. For instance, Chinese slang commonly replaces words with similar sounding words or written characters with similar looking written characters (Qian et al., 2023). UGC might also combine words from multiple languages (e.g., “C’est trop mainstream”). WMT 2022 found that translation errors were overall more prevalent in MTs of UGC (reviews) compared to news content (Kocmi et al., 2022).

At the other end of the spectrum is highly specialised text and terminology. Some areas in particular, such as legal or scientific contexts, rely on precise language and getting the translation of such terms exactly correct is paramount (Semenov et al., 2023).

3.3 Types and Causes of Errors

To understand what kind of errors might arise in MT, Popovic (2021) asked annotators to identify and label errors in English-Croatian and English-Serbian translations of user reviews as well as English-German translations of TED Talks (using both online and in-house MT systems). Similarly, WMT 2022 manually analysed a subset of English-Croatian machine translations (Kocmi et al., 2022). They both found that a common category were **rephrasing errors**. These arise when the translation follows

is often simpler than an original. This is referred to as translationese. As a result, **back-translation**, that is translating an already translated text, might be easier than forward-translating a genuine source text (Burchell et al., 2022).

⁵The datasets added at WMT 2022 and 2023 include product descriptions, Reddit posts, customer-agent chat data, speech data and text from manuals.

the structure of the source but this does not make sense in the target language (i.e., rephrasing is required but not applied) or when rephrasing in the translation is not applied correctly. An example is translating “and so am I” word for word as “und so bin ich” in German instead of the correct “und ich auch”.

More recently, [Bawden and Sagot \(2023\)](#) tested MT systems on their robustness to non-standard text as part of WMT 2023. This included non-standard variants of words due to spelling errors, devowelling (e.g., “nvr” instead of “never”), truncation (e.g., “intro” instead of “introduction”) or phonetically inspired spelling (e.g., “wot” instead of “what”). They found such phenomena remain challenging for translation but this might depend on how frequent the non-standard word is in the training data. For example, “tho” (for “though”) was correctly translated whereas “tmro” (for “tomorrow”), proved more difficult. When a non-standard word led to an error it was either omitted or left untranslated.

Other frequent causes of errors reported by [Popovic \(2021\)](#), [Macketanz et al. \(2022\)](#) and [Kocmi et al. \(2022\)](#) are [noun phrases](#) and [ambiguity](#). Noun phrases are sequences of nouns (and possibly adjectives) such as “slime mold”, which in German translates as “Schleimpilz” but would sometimes be translated as “Schlamm” or “Schlamm mold”. Ambiguous words are, for example, words with multiple meanings, such as the English words “run”, “sound” or “set”. MT systems especially struggle when translating infrequently used word meanings, showing bias toward more common word senses ([Campolungo et al., 2022](#)).

Lastly, [Wang et al. \(2021b\)](#) tested commercial MT systems on numerical translations, such as handling of integers, decimals or separators and numbers presented as words. They found that all systems struggle with handling different [locale conventions](#) for the use of separators (e.g., using ‘;’ instead of ‘.’ as the decimal point) and that they struggle with numerical translation in general (e.g., they were more likely to mistranslate larger integers and decimals with longer decimal parts).

3.4 Critical Errors

Some types of MT errors are more egregious than others. Correspondingly, it is common to distinguish between [meaning-preserving perturbations \(MPPs\)](#) and [meaning-altering perturbations \(MAPs\)](#). Examples of MPPs include removing or replacing punctuation or determiners and changing words to uppercase or lowercase; whereas MAPs include the removal of negation markers, replacing words with antonyms and any other removal, duplication, insertion or replacement of random content words ([Kanojia et al., 2021](#)). A translation with MPP might still be considered acceptable whereas a translation containing any MAP should be flagged as incorrect.⁶

MAPs have also been called [critical errors](#) or [catastrophic errors](#) in the literature ([Specia et al., 2020b, 2021](#); [Zerva et al., 2022a](#); [Alves et al., 2022](#); [Karpinska et al., 2022](#)). Although the exact definition of these terms can vary slightly between articles they all broadly agree that critical errors are MAPs as described above. Additionally, many specify [sentiment reversal](#) or introduction of toxicity as well as incorrectly translating [named entities](#) and [numbers](#) as standalone critical error categories although they are implied by the MAP definition.

WMT 2020 held a shared task on MT robustness, evaluating the frequency and type of catastrophic errors produced by MT systems ([Specia et al., 2020b](#)). Most catastrophic errors were tagged as belonging to the ‘other’ category. From the provided labeled categories, a large number were labeled as mistranslations of named entities. Next, sentiment reversal errors were frequent followed by introduction of toxicity (profanity, violence, hate or abuse) but the proportions of these two categories differed by language pair and text source.

⁶Whether an error is meaning altering depends on the specific sentence rather than the type of error. Even a missing comma can make a big difference to the overall meaning of a sentence as demonstrated by the classic example of “let’s eat, Grandma” compared to “let’s eat Grandma”. Similarly, a sentence can still retain its meaning even if some of the words are omitted, resulting in awkward phrasing but nothing more egregious.

In the 2021 WMT QE shared task, the organisers translated text using a number of off-the-shelf translation systems and found that critical errors were rare [Specia et al. \(2021\)](#). Specifically, they made up 9–28% of the data depending on the language pair. They noted that this might be higher than commonly seen in practice as they were translating UGC text consisting of Wikipedia comments with high chances of containing the type of content they were targeting such as toxicity or named entities. It is possibly also more challenging than other domains, such as news content.

[Saadany et al. \(2023\)](#) similarly observed that sentiment reversal errors were common in social media posts. They identified common features of UGC, such as non-standard orthography or the use of dialectic expressions, as contributing causes. Other, more general, linguistic phenomena, such as words having multiple meanings, also posed a challenge to sentiment translations. Social media posts might be particularly challenging in this regard as they are often short and so might not provide sufficient context to disambiguate words with multiple meanings.

Lastly, [Guerreiro et al. \(2023b\)](#) annotated a large dataset of neural machine translation (NMT) output with types of critical errors, with a particular emphasis on identifying translations with hallucinations. Hallucinations are translated content that is unfaithful to, or in some way detached from, the source text. It is a rare but potentially catastrophic type of error. [Guerreiro et al. \(2023b\)](#) consider hallucinations as distinct to mistranslation errors, such as of named entities, as these are incorrect rather than detached content.⁷

4 Measuring Translation Quality

4.1 Overview

The gold standard in MT quality annotations are human generated scores. Raters can be asked to give a on overall scalar quality score (e.g., on a scale of 0–100) or to identify errors within the translation from which a final score is computed. However, the degree to which a translation is considered ‘good’ can be subjective. One has to weigh several different dimensions against each other such as fluency, style and accuracy. See [Appendix A](#) for an illustrative example.

Additionally, what constitutes a major error can be use case dependant. If an application of MT is to communicate on a professional level with customers or clients, then it is likely that any grammatical errors are considered major, even though they might not affect the meaning of the text. In some contexts, such as literary translations, capturing the tone and style of the original text (e.g., the use of slang) is as important as grammatical correctness.⁸ But if the sole goal is to understand the original text, then minor grammatical errors and style deviations might not be substantive.

Human evaluation can also be costly and time consuming. Therefore a substantial amount of MT research has focused on automating evaluation. This necessitates the creation of high quality human annotated datasets relying on professional translators or linguists.⁹ Ideally multiple evaluators are used with protocols in place to ensure consensus can be reached.

This section gives an overview of different methods developed for evaluating translation quality. This is followed by a discussion of why human, let alone automated, evaluation of translation remains a challenging problem as evidenced by lack of consistent agreement between raters or even different scoring schemes. It then briefly outlines approaches to automated MT evaluation.

⁷Hallucinations might have elsewhere been called [addition errors](#).

⁸Take for instance the English idiom “it’s raining cats and dogs”. At the very least, a translation should capture the intended meaning “it’s raining heavily” instead of outputting a word-for-word translation. Additionally, it might be more appropriate to find a similar idiomatic expression in the target language to preserve the style of the source. For example, a suitable choice for translations into Czech might be the equivalent of “it’s raining wheelbarrows”.

⁹Crowd sourced evaluators do not always agree with professional translators and might score MT systems more leniently ([Läubli et al., 2020](#); [Freitag et al., 2021a](#); [Chelba et al., 2020](#)).

4.2 Types of Quality Assessments

One approach to MT quality evaluation is to ask annotators to find the minimum number of edits (e.g., word insertions, deletions, substitutions or shifts) needed to make the translation acceptable. The final output is usually a ratio of the number of edits relative to the total number of **tokens** in the text. This is commonly referred to as **post-edit ratios** or **human-mediated translation edit rate (HTER)** (Snover et al., 2006). See Table 1 for an example.

Another common approach is to give a single scalar quality score.¹⁰ The most frequently used example are **direct assessments (DAs)**, which are given on a scale of 0–100 with guidelines on how to map the severity of errors to ranges of scores on the scale (Graham et al., 2013; Guzmán et al., 2019). For example, a score of 0–10 is an incorrect translation, 30–50 is a translation with major mistakes and 70–90 is a translation that closely preserves the meaning of the source. The popularity of **DAs** is partly due to the fact that the scoring scheme can be simple to communicate and is therefore often used to crowd-source the annotations. However, crowd-sourcing data does not always result in high-quality annotations. Additionally, Table 2 shows an example of a translation scored using DA by six annotators where there is a clear split in how the annotators interpret and apply the scoring scheme.

Recent iterations of **WMT** have also asked raters to give a 0–6 **scalar quality metric (SQM)** score following their DA score. This additional evaluation step was suggested to stabilize the DA scores across annotators (Kocmi et al., 2022). On the SQM scale 0 is labeled as ‘Nonsense, no meaning preserved’, 2 is labeled as ‘Some meaning preserved’, 4 is labeled as ‘Most meaning preserved and few grammar mistakes’ and 6 is labeled as ‘Perfect meaning and grammar’. WMT refer to this as **DA+SQM** scores (Freitag et al., 2023).

In contrast to these approaches, the **multidimensional quality metric (MQM)** framework asks evaluators to label errors and classify them by category (‘accuracy’, ‘fluency’, ‘terminology’, ‘style’ and ‘locale convention’, see Appendix B.1 for more information) and severity (neutral, minor, major, critical) (Freitag et al., 2021a; Kocmi et al., 2022). The severity categories have a proposed weight (e.g., 0, 1, 5 and 10 respectively) and a single MQM score is calculated as a sum of the individual error scores. Since MQM is a general framework, the value of the weights and the category of errors they apply to can vary by application. Appendix B.1 describes two MQM weighting schemes, both of which have been used in the last three years of the WMT metrics task (Freitag et al., 2021b, 2022, 2023). As shown in Table 3, MQM annotations are more fine-grained than DA output.

For both DA and MQM it is also possible to apply some kind of normalisation as a last step. *Z*-score normalisation per annotator is often applied as some annotators may consistently give lower or higher scores. This might be due to some annotators being more lenient in their definition of quality or it might reflect differences in how the annotators interpret and use the provided scales. Additionally, MQM scores are usually divided by sentence length as longer sentences have more opportunities for errors than short sentences and overall MQM score is a sum of all the errors. Additionally, MQM scores can be inverted so that they have the same direction as the DA scores with low values representing poor quality and high values representing high quality.

4.3 Consistency Issues

The above described scoring schemes are not always consistent with each other. Consequently, the choice of scoring scheme can affect which MT system is ranked as best. Recent research has shown that DA or SQM scores do not correlate well with MQM scores at the segment-level (e.g., sentence), although SQM and MQM are aligned in the aggregate at the system-level (Freitag et al., 2021a,b).

¹⁰Historically, it has also been common to give a separate fluency and accuracy score, but these were observed to correlate.

Source	The urban morphology of these two local watersheds tends to draw them inexorably closer together .
Machine Translation	Die urbane Morphologie dieser beiden lokalen Wasserscheiden tendiert dazu , sie unaufhaltsam zusammenzubringen . <EOS>
Post-Edit Translation	Die urbane Morphologie dieser beiden lokalen Wassereinzugsgebiete führt dazu , dass sie unaufhaltsam näher zusammenrücken .
Word Tags	OK OK OK OK OK OK BAD BAD OK OK BAD OK BAD OK OK
HTER	0.312500

Table 1: An example from the WMT 2022 English-German post-edit dataset (Zerva et al., 2022a). Tokens tagged as ‘bad’ in the machine translation are shown in **bold**. Note that each token (including punctuation) has a word tag and an end-of-sentence (EOS) token is included in case of omissions at the end of the sentence.

Source	Miller then bowled the English skipper Yardley to end England’s innings at 496.
Machine Translation	Miller bog dann den englischen Skipper Yardley, um Englands Innings bei 496 zu beenden.
Annotator DA Scores	100, 100, 85, 51, 50, 40
Mean DA Score	71

Table 2: An example from the WMT 2022 English-German DA dataset where the sentence has been scored by six human annotators (Zerva et al., 2022a).

Source	But the sound is too quiet for any of us to ever hear.			
Machine Translation	Aber der Klang ist zu leise für jeden von uns, um ihn jemals zu hören .			
Annotation ID	<u>Error Span</u>	<u>Category</u>	<u>Severity</u>	<u>Score</u>
Span 1	Klang	Terminology/Inconsistent use of terminology	Minor	1
Span 2	jeden von uns, um ihn jemals zu höre	Accuracy/Mistranslation	Major	5
Total MQM	6			
Normalised MQM	0.6471			

Table 3: An example from the WMT 2021 English-German MQM dataset (Freitag et al., 2021b). The total **MQM** is a sum of the scores of each error span, and the normalised MQM divides this score by the number of tokens in the translated sentence and then subtracts this value from one.

Additionally, WMT 2023 findings note that DA+SQM produces fewer clusters between the submitted MT systems compared to MQM (Kocmi et al., 2023). They suggest this implies DA+SQM fails to pick up on small differences in translation performance whereas MQM is more sensitive.

There might be disagreement even when using slightly different versions of the same scoring scheme. The WMT 2021 metrics shared task observed low agreement in segment-level MQM annotations of TED talks data between two different MQM weighting schemes (see Appendix B.1 for description of both) as well as between individual annotators, although the overall system rankings were consistent (Freitag et al., 2021b). They posit that TED talks might be more challenging type of content given it consists of transcripts of speech rather than written structured text such as the more commonly used news data. They encourage further work on establishing a robust ground truth.

The various issues around consistency of scores show that one needs to consider carefully what available data to use and to take their limitations into account when drawing conclusions about MT system performance. At the moment, the MQM framework is endorsed by a number of researchers as preferable to DA although it also has its limitations (Freitag et al., 2021a,b).

4.4 Inter-rater Agreement

Inter-rater agreement can vary by scoring scheme as well as language pair. Fomicheva et al. (2021) report inter-rater agreement between three to four annotators who provided DA scores for four language pairs (German-Chinese, Russian-German, Romanian-English, Estonian-English) with correlations between the annotators ranging from 0.59-0.81. Freitag et al. (2021a) reported better agreement between MQM annotators compared to SQM (even when using professional translators). They suggest this is because it is difficult to consistently reflect different types and severity of errors with a single numerical value across raters, making MQM preferable. Table 4 displays a summary of the reported inter-rater agreement correlations for two language pairs and scoring schemes.

Language Pair	MQM			SQM		
	min	average	max	min	average	max
English-German	0.536	0.584	0.663	0.221	0.304	0.447
Chinese-English	0.365	0.412	0.488	0.008	0.169	0.517

Table 4: Pairwise inter-rate agreement values (min, max and average) by language pair and scoring scheme (MQM and SQM) reported in Freitag et al. (2021a).

There are numerous examples in the literature of protocols for encouraging consistency across annotators and deriving a single ground-truth quality score. Evaluations are more robust if the full document context is provided rather than only presenting annotators with isolated sentences (Läubli et al., 2020; Akhbardeh et al., 2021). Similarly, it might be preferable to ask annotators to evaluate the target translation by comparing it to the source text rather than to a reference translation (Fomicheva and Specia, 2016; Freitag et al., 2022).¹¹ It is also recommended to rely on professional translators and common practice to either average their scores or bring in additional evaluators when the disagreement is larger than a defined threshold until consensus is reached (Fomicheva et al., 2022; Blain et al., 2023).

Alternatively, Basile et al. (2021) have argued that instead of forcing annotator consensus in natural language processing (NLP) tasks, one should incorporate it into the modelling and evaluation. The reasoning is that annotator disagreement reflects subjectivity inherent in these task and

¹¹Sometimes the terms bilingual and monolingual evaluation are used to distinguish between whether the evaluator is comparing the target translation to the original source text or a reference translation respectively.

corresponds to instances where multiple annotations are equally appropriate. One example is to output soft labels and compare those against the distribution of labels across annotators.

4.5 Automated Evaluation

Automatic metrics are built to achieve a ‘good’ correlation with human judgements of translation quality, whether those be [DA](#), [MQM](#) or some other scheme. Metrics are generally computed at the [word-](#) or [sentence-level](#) but some are designed specifically to be averaged over an entire corpus of text ([system-level](#)), which can be useful when the goal is to rank [MT](#) systems.

A key distinction is between [reference-based](#) and [reference-free](#) (or [QE](#)) evaluation metrics. For reference-based metrics, the task is to compare a translation from an [MT](#) system (frequently referred to as the [candidate](#), [hypothesis](#) or [target](#)) to a human generated [reference](#) translation as a way of arriving at the final score.

Reliance on a reference for evaluation can lead to [reference-bias](#). This refers to scoring translations that are superficially similar to the reference more highly than translations that are equally good but deviate from the reference in some way.¹² Some of this may be alleviated by using multiple references for comparison ([Dreyer and Marcu, 2012](#)).

There are several categories of automated reference-based evaluation metrics, all still commonly used in the literature. One approach is to measure the amount of editing required for the target to match the reference ([Snover et al., 2006](#)). An alternative is to count [n-gram](#) matches between the target and the reference, an approach taken by [BLEU](#) ([Papineni et al., 2002](#)) or [chrF](#) ([Popović, 2015](#)). However, all of these metrics penalise translations that are correct but use different word choices compared to the provided references. More recent approaches have made use of [PLMs](#) to create contextual embedding representations of the target and the reference. A quality score is computed either based on how similar the embeddings are (e.g., [BERTScore](#), [Zhang et al. \(2020\)](#)), or with a model trained for the task (e.g., [COMET](#), [Rei et al. \(2020a\)](#)). These modern metrics have been shown to be more robust to paraphrased reference translations ([Zhang et al., 2020](#)) and to outperform string matching metrics like [BLEU](#) ([Freitag et al., 2022](#)). [Appendix C](#) provides a more detailed overview of reference-based evaluation metrics.

In contrast, in reference-free evaluation, or [QE](#), the metric only considers the target translation and the [source](#) text. [QE](#) is the focus of the rest of this report.

5 Quality Estimation (QE) Data

5.1 Overview

[QE](#) is usually carried out at [word-level](#) or [sentence-level](#). Word-level [QE](#) is typically a binary task which predicts a value of ‘OK’ or ‘BAD’ for each word in the translated text. By contrast, the aim of sentence-level [QE](#) is to predict a single score that represents the quality of a sentence.¹³

A standard approach to [QE](#) is to use supervised machine learning to predict the quality of translations. The training data will comprise of pairs of [source](#) and [target](#) text and a human generated quality score. Supervised approaches to [QE](#) rely on datasets annotated by human linguists, which are expensive and time-consuming to obtain. This limits the number of available datasets for [QE](#) training and their domain representativeness. Moreover, for some language pairs the overall quality of [MT](#) is higher, which can limit the number of low-scoring translations. This can, in turn, impact ability of supervised [QE](#) systems to learn how to predict the full range of quality scores.

¹²Human evaluators are also susceptible to [reference-bias](#) ([Fomicheva and Specia, 2016](#)).

¹³Some tasks may also consider segment-level [QE](#), which may consider text longer than a sentence, but not as long as a document. Document-level predictions have also appeared in the literature, but are not as common ([Specia et al., 2020a](#)).

This section describes the available QE datasets. These are split into real-word human annotated data used for model training and synthetically created challenge sets for fine-grained evaluation. Links to the datasets described in this section can be found in [Appendix H](#).

5.2 Core Datasets

Core QE datasets consist of pairs of [source](#) and [target](#) text with human quality annotations following one of the available assessment schemes such as [DAs](#), [post-edits](#) or [MQM](#). The target sentences are produced using [MT](#) systems, meaning that the data contain real translation errors and their frequency and type might vary by language pair or MT system.

A summary of the data made available for the QE shared task at [WMT 2023](#) is shown in [Table 5](#). The majority of the 19 language pairs are scored using DA, frequently combined with post-edit annotations.¹⁴ Most language pairs have in the order of 7–10 thousand sentences. There are also four MQM annotated language pairs, which are generally better resourced. Note that Hebrew-English and English-Farsi were both treated as zero-shot (i.e., they were not included in the training data). Not all of the data were curated specifically for the QE shared task. For example, some of the MQM data originated from the metrics shared task at WMT and was repurposed for QE by discarding the reference translations.

Source text for 10 of the DA language pairs are taken from Wikipedia articles. In contrast, Russian-English dataset includes Russian proverbs and Reddit data from various subreddits, with a particular focus on politics and religion, to make it particularly challenging for [MT](#). The remaining DA data are multi-domain, spanning the general, news, health, legal, culture/tourism, education and scientific domains.

The MQM data are restricted to four language pairs. They cover English-German, Chinese-English and English-Russian extensively and also contain a small set of Hebrew-English examples. Combined, the datasets comprise multiple domains, including news, TED talks, e-commerce, social and conversational. Although limited in terms of language pairs, these data are more varied and place greater emphasis on [UGC](#) relative to the majority of the DA data. The English-Russian and Hebrew-English data were annotated following slightly different annotation guidelines to the other language pairs although they were then re-scored to match (the two approaches are referred to as Unbabel’s and Google’s MQM schemes respectively and are described in [Appendix B.1](#)).

The [word-level](#) QE sub-task labels are obtained using either the MQM or post-edited data. The label ‘OK’ is used if the token is translated correctly and ‘BAD’ otherwise. The source text is not annotated; however, [omission errors](#) are accounted for by labelling the token to the right side of the omitted text as ‘BAD’.

5.3 Challenge Sets

[Challenge sets](#) are created to probe the specific weaknesses and strengths of models. In the case of QE, the focus is usually on understanding what types of translation errors QE metrics are good (or bad) at differentiating. It is common to identify a general taxonomy of error categories (and a corresponding severity classification) and for each category to create pairs of correct and incorrect translation examples. Metrics are evaluated on whether they score the erroneous translations as lower compared to the correct examples. They can also be evaluated on whether they are sensitive to error severity.

For example, the [ACES dataset](#) ([Amrhein et al., 2022, 2023](#)) has 10 broad error categories that are classed as minor or major (see [Appendix B.2](#)) whereas the [DEMETER dataset](#) ([Karpinska et al., 2022](#))

¹⁴A key source for these data are the [Multilingual Quality Estimation and Post-Editing Dataset \(MLQE-PE\)](#).

Language Pair	Number of Sentences			DA	PE	MQM	Data Source	Release
	Train	Dev	Test					
English-German	10,000	-	-	✓	✓		Wikipedia	2021/22
English-Chinese	10,000	-	-	✓	✓		Wikipedia	2021/22
Russian-English	10,000	-	-	✓	✓		Reddit	2021/22
Romanian-English	10,000	-	-	✓	✓		Wikipedia	2021/22
Estonian-English	10,000	-	-	✓	✓		Wikipedia	2021/22
Nepali-English	10,000	-	-	✓	✓		Wikipedia	2021/22
Sinhala-English	10,000	-	-	✓	✓		Wikipedia	2021/22
Pashto-English	2,000	-	-	✓	✓		Wikipedia	2021/22
Khmer-English	2,000	-	-	✓	✓		Wikipedia	2021/22
English-Japanese	2,000	-	-	✓	✓		Wikipedia	2021/22
English-Czech	2,000	-	-	✓	✓		Wikipedia	2021/22
English-Yoruba	1,010	-	-	✓	✓		Wikipedia	2021/22
English-Marathi	27,000	1,000	1,086	✓	✓		multi-domain/corpus	2022/23
English-Hindi	7,000	1,000	1,074	✓			multi-domain/corpus	2023
English-Gujarati	7,000	1,000	1,075	✓			multi-domain/corpus	2023
English-Tamil	7,000	1,000	1,067	✓			multi-domain/corpus	2023
English-Telugu	7,000	1,023	1,000	✓			multi-domain/corpus	2023
English-Farsi	-	-	1,000		✓		news (multi-domain)	2023
English-German	30,425	-	1,897			✓	multi-domain	2021/23
English-Russian	17,144	-	-			✓	multi-domain	2021/22
Chinese-English	36,851	-	1,675			✓	multi-domain	2021/23
Hebrew-English	-	-	1,182			✓	multi-domain	2023

Table 5: Overview of [WMT 2023 QE](#) data showing the number of sentences in the train, development and test datasets and the scoring scheme of [DA](#), [post-edits \(PE\)](#) and [MQM](#), adapted from [Kocmi et al. \(2023\)](#).

has 31 error categories that are classed as minor, major or critical as well as four baseline categories to establish lower and upper bounds on metric output (see [Appendix B.3](#)). The DEMETR dataset consists entirely of translations into English from 10 languages (French, Italian, Spanish, German, Czech, Polish, Russian, Hindi, Chinese and Japanese) with 3,500 examples per language pair.¹⁵ The ACES dataset covers 48 languages and 146 language pairs but some language pairs have significantly more examples than others (the vast majority of language pairs have fewer than 100 examples while a small handful of language pairs have a several thousand examples).

In contrast, the [MT-TestSuite](#) ([Macketanz et al., 2022](#)) is limited to German-English translations in both directions with 2500 examples made publicly available for each. The dataset consists of source sentences accompanied by hand-crafted regular expressions that capture patterns of characters and words that a good or a bad translation would exhibit. For example, given the German sentence “Er las gerne Novellen” and the error category of ‘false friends’, the positive regular expression checks whether the English translation contains the word “novellas” or “short stories” and the negative regular expression checks whether the translation contains the word “novels” or “novelty”. The authors have applied the regular expressions to authentic MT outputs to create ‘GOOD’ and ‘BAD’ sentence-level labelled data for evaluating QE systems ([Avramidis et al., 2018](#); [Avramidis and Macketanz, 2022](#)). Errors in the MT-TestSuite span the full spectrum from punctuation errors to negation errors but no severity labels are provided.

The error examples in challenge sets are primarily synthetic, which means that the errors might not be ones commonly encountered in practice. For example, in the ACES dataset ([Amrhein et al., 2023](#)), one error category is ‘wrong language’, which tests metric ability to distinguish between similar languages, such as Catalan and Spanish. QE metrics that do poorly in this category might still perform well in applied settings.

5.4 Critical Error Data

The QE shared task at WMT 2021 and 2022 held subtasks on [critical error detection \(CED\)](#) for which they released [sentence-level](#) annotations. [Table 6](#) gives an overview of the available data by language pair.

The data and goal of the tasks between the two WMT iterations differed. In the 2021 edition, the organisers annotated genuine translations from MT systems of UGC text (Wikipedia comments). In contrast, the 2022 edition created a synthetic [challenge set](#) from news data using the [SMAUG framework](#) ([Alves et al., 2022](#)). The SMAUG framework uses automated methods to generate [critical errors](#) by perturbing good quality translations (e.g., by adding or removing content words or negation markers) ([Alves et al., 2022](#)). The organisers kept the synthetic errors to at most 5% of the dataset to reflect rarity of such errors in real world data.

There were also some subtle differences in how critical errors were defined. The 2021 annotation guidelines specified a subset of critical error categories; introduction of toxicity (hate, violence or profanity), deviations that may bring a risk to the reader, [sentiment reversal](#) and mistranslations of [named entities](#) and [numbers](#). While these are fairly comprehensive, it is conceivable that the translations included meaning altering errors that did not fall into any of these categories and so were not annotated as critical. The five critical error categories used in the 2022 task were defined similarly but somewhat more broadly as [additions](#), [omissions](#), sentiment reversal and named entity and number errors.

The [DEMETR dataset](#) described in the previous section also includes examples of critical errors. They mostly map onto the five categories used at WMT 2022.

¹⁵For each language pair, [Karpinska et al. \(2022\)](#) collected 100 translations and each was perturbed 35 different ways to create an example of each of the 31 errors and the four baseline categories.

Lastly, the WMT English-Russian MQM data were originally annotated by Unbabel¹⁶ using a scheme that includes the critical error category, defined as MAP (see Appendix B.1). The data was re-scored before it was released as part of the WMT QE subtask, treating critical errors as major errors. However, some of the original 2022 annotations are also publicly available.

Released by	Type	Data Source	Language pair	Sentences	% Errors
WMT QE 2021	Authentic	Wikipedia comments	English-Chinese	8,859	15.9
			English-Czech	9,476	17.3
			English-German	9,878	28.1
			English-Japanese	9,658	9.3

WMT QE 2022	Synthetic	news	English-German	173,291	5.8
Unbabel MQM annotations 2022	Authentic	multi-domain	Portuguese-English	44,862	5.8
			English-Russian	1,215	7.5
			Chinese-English	3,500	28.6
			Czech-English	3,500	28.6
			French-English	3,500	28.6
			German-English	3,500	28.6
			Hindi-English	3,500	28.6
			Italian-English	3,500	28.6
			Japanese-English	3,500	28.6
			Polish-English	3,500	28.6
DEMETR dataset	Synthetic	multi-domain	Russian-English	3,500	28.6
			Spanish-English	3,500	28.6

Table 6: Overview of publicly available datasets with critical error annotations. The data is primarily from WMT 2021 and 2022 CED tasks as well as the DEMETR dataset. Included are also the original Unbabel annotations of the WMT 2022 English-Russian MQM data. The table presents the number of sentences in each dataset that are publicly available and approximately what percentage of those are examples of critical errors. It also indicates the text domain and whether the errors are synthetic or authentic.

5.5 Hallucinations Data

Recently, several datasets have been released with examples of authentic MT output annotated for hallucination errors. Guerreiro et al. (2023b) developed a taxonomy of hallucinations and distinguished between *strongly detached* and *fully detached hallucinations* based on whether the content is at least partially related to the source or not at all. They also defined inadequate translations with erroneous repetitions as a separate category called *oscillatory hallucinations*. They released 3,415 German-English sentences that were all translations of news of which about 9% are hallucinations. Following their approach and taxonomy, WMT 2023 also released a small dataset of authentic hallucination data for most of their test language pairs (Blain et al., 2023). The biggest dataset is for English-German with 1422 sentences but only 9 of those are hallucinations. In contrast, the low resource language pairs have in the order of 810–830 sentences with around 75 hallucinations each.

Additionally, Dale et al. (2023) released the HalOmi dataset, which has hallucination (partial or full) and omission annotations. The dataset consists of 18 language pairs (9 unique language pairings with translations in both directions) with around 150 sentences per language pair. They found that hallucination errors are more frequent for low resource language pairs.

¹⁶<https://unbabel.com/>

Team / Company Name	Model Name	Category	PLM(s)	Output Sentence	Word	WMT 2023 Metrics	QE	Citation
Unbabel	COMET-QE	fine-tuned	XLM-R-L	✓	✓			Rei et al. (2020b)
Unbabel-IST	COMET-KIWI	fine-tuned	InfoXLM-L RemBERT XLM-R-L XLM-R-XL XLM-R-XXL	✓	✓		✓	Rei et al. (2022b, 2023)
	xCOMET-QE	fine-tuned	XLM-R-XL XLM-R-XXL	✓	✓		✓	Guerreiro et al. (2023a)
Microsoft	GEMBA-MQM	LLM prompt-based	GPT-4	✓			✓	Kocmi and Federmann (2023b)
Google	MetricX-23-QE	fine-tuned	mT5 PaLM 2 Bison	✓			✓	Juraska et al. (2023)
NJUNLP	-	fine-tuned	XLM-R-L	✓	✓		✓	Geng et al. (2023)
HW-TSC	CrossQE	fine-tuned	XLM-R InfoXLM RemBERT COMET-KIWI	✓			✓	Li et al. (2023)
	KG-BERTScore	embedding similarity					✓	Wu et al. (2023b)
IOL Research	-	fine-tuned	XLM-R-L mDeBERTa RemBERT InfoXLM-L	✓	✓		✓	Yan et al. (2023)

Table 7: List of **black-box QE** models referenced in this report by team. The table shows model name (if one exists), the explored **PLMs**, whether the model outputs **sentence-** or **word-level** scores (**KG-BERTScore** was designed for **system-level QE**) and whether the model was submitted to the metrics or QE shared task at WMT 2023.

6 QE Models

6.1 Overview

A high-level taxonomy of QE models can be defined along two dimensions. The first dimension is whether the model has access to features or additional output of the MT system. Models that treat the underlying MT system as unknown are called **black-box QE** and are built using features created from the **source** and **target** text only. In contrast, **glass-box QE** models also have access to features derived from the internal state or some additional output of the MT system.

The second dimension is whether the method involves a learning or training phase. Methods that do not require training are more common in **reference-based evaluation** where the lexical similarity between features of the **reference** and target translation can be compared (Papineni et al., 2002; Popović, 2015; Lavie and Agarwal, 2007; Zhang et al., 2020). However, similar methods can also be used to compare the source text to the target (Wu et al., 2023b). Other approaches that do not require training estimate quality from the MT system uncertainty (Fomicheva et al., 2020b) or use a decoder-based LLM (Lu et al., 2024; Kocmi and Federmann, 2023a).

The majority of approaches to QE are supervised machine learning models that are trained on black-box features. Early models used standard machine learning algorithms, such as **support vector machines (SVMs)** (Specia et al., 2010; Hardmeier et al., 2012; Soricut et al., 2012), decision trees (Moreau and Vogel, 2012), and Gaussian processes (Cohn and Specia, 2013; Shah et al., 2015). As deep learning became more common, **neural networks (NNs)** and, in particular, **recurrent neural networks (RNNs)** were used for QE (Kreutzer et al., 2015; Kim and Lee, 2016; Martins et al., 2016). Modern architectures typically add a regression or classification head (depending on whether the objective is **sentence-level** or **word-level evaluation**) onto a pre-trained **transformer**-based encoder and then fine-tune the model with QE data.

This section begins with a discussion on black-box and glass-box features and then defines various categories of modern QE models. Recent trends in QE model development are then covered.

6.2 Features

Early QE approaches relied on manually designed **black-box** features to capture relationships between the **source** and **target** sentences. Examples of such features include sentence length, average source word length and average number of occurrences of all words within the translated sentence (Specia et al., 2010). By 2019 many, but not all, submissions to the QE shared task at WMT relied on encoder-only PLMs to encode the source and target text instead of using manually created features (Fonseca et al., 2019). It is likely that the dominance of encoder-only PLMs is due to their ability to capture more complex relationships between the source and target text.

There have also been some studies that used features obtained from the underlying MT system, known as **glass-box** features. Examples include using the softmax output of the MT model or estimating uncertainty of the MT system using **Monte Carlo dropout** (Gal and Ghahramani, 2016). These features have been either used directly to estimate quality (Fomicheva et al., 2020b), or used alongside black-box features as inputs to supervised QE models (Moura et al., 2020; Wang et al., 2021a).

At the WMT 2021 QE shared task, one of the top three performing submissions used glass-box features (Specia et al., 2021). However, at WMT 2022 purely black-box models outperformed all glass-box approaches (Zerva et al., 2022a) and by 2023 none of the submissions used glass-box features (Blain et al., 2023).

There may be scenarios where models using glass-box features are still competitive with models that only use black-box features. Specia et al. (2020a) suggested that glass-box QE models may

offer a better trade-off between accuracy and efficiency than large, pre-trained models with only black-box features; however, this hypothesis has not been fully investigated in the literature. As this report focuses on the [SOTA](#), only black-box QE models are covered in subsequent sections with some further discussion on glass-box QE approaches in [Appendix D](#).

6.3 Model Categories

A summary of [SOTA](#) models is displayed in [Table 7](#) with more detailed descriptions of the individual models provided in [Appendix E](#). The models only rely on [black-box QE](#) features and are grouped into one of three categories.

The first category is a [fine-tuned QE model](#), which is a supervised method that uses some [PLM](#) as a base model and fine-tunes it using [QE](#) data. This approach is currently dominant amongst [QE](#) submissions at [WMT](#) ([Blain et al., 2023](#); [Freitag et al., 2023](#)). The various submissions can differ in the choice of PLM, the output of the model (e.g., [word-](#) or [sentence-level](#) predictions), the selection of loss function, the additional architecture added to the PLM and the training procedures. Many of these decisions will be discussed in upcoming sections.

The second category is an [embedding similarity QE model](#) that also uses a PLM but without carrying out any additional training or fine-tuning. In this case, the PLM is used to encode the [source](#) and [target](#) text, and a prediction of quality is calculated based on some measure of similarity between the two embeddings. This approach is more often applied to [reference-based evaluation](#) where the similarity of the [reference](#) and target text is compared. However, a reference-free embedding similarity model named [KG-BERTScore](#), which compares the source and target embeddings, ([Wu et al., 2023b](#)) achieved a joint third place ranking at the metrics shared task at [WMT 2023](#). [KG-BERTScore](#) is designed as a [system-level](#) metric to compare the overall quality of different [MT](#) systems rather than individual outputs of a single system.

Recent developments have seen a third category, [LLM prompt-based QE models](#), evolve ([Lu et al., 2024](#); [Kocmi and Federmann, 2023a](#)). These models use an [LLM](#)¹⁷ and develop a prompting strategy for estimating translation quality. Although this approach is not yet dominant, it may attract more research attention in the near-future and has the advantage of not requiring training data.

6.4 Model Architectures

While there are some [QE](#) models that only produce [sentence-level](#) scores, there is a trend towards [black-box fine-tuned QE models](#) to be [multi-task](#), training them to predict both [word-](#) and [sentence-level](#) scores. This approach appears to improve the sentence-level performance (compared to training a model to only predict the sentence-level scores) despite the word-level performance being generally lower than sentence-level ([Blain et al., 2023](#)).

[Figure 1](#) shows a generic example of a multi-task architecture. Models vary in the design of the feed-forward networks or the aggregation or pooling strategy. For example, [Geng et al. \(2023\)](#) average the token embeddings to create a sentence-level representation whereas [Rei et al. \(2023\)](#) use the [CLS] token. Additionally, the format of the input might differ between models; for example, [Li et al. \(2023\)](#) design their input to take the [source](#) and [target](#) sentences, s and t , concatenated in both orders¹⁸: $[s, t]$ and $[t, s]$.

There are also different choices of loss function for multi-task architectures. [Rei et al. \(2023\)](#), [Guerreiro et al. \(2023a\)](#) and [Yan et al. \(2023\)](#) all use a weighted sum of the mean squared error (for

¹⁷In the context of this report, a [LLM](#) refers to a large [PLM](#) with decoder-only architecture, such as [GPT-4](#) ([OpenAI et al., 2023](#)) or [LLaMA](#) ([Touvron et al., 2023](#)).

¹⁸In related work, [Eo et al. \(2021\)](#) found that the order of the [source](#) and [target](#) sentences in the input to [PLM](#)-based models influenced the performance of the model.

Figure 1: A representation of a generic architecture for [fine-tuned QE models](#) that takes text in the [source](#) and [target](#) languages as input and produces a [sentence-level](#) score and [word-level](#) labels as output. Not all approaches will produce both outputs and there will be different strategies for arriving at the sentence and word representations that are fed into the feed-forward neural networks.

[sentence-level](#) regression) and cross-entropy loss (for word-level classification). However, [Geng et al. \(2023\)](#) experimented with including a margin ranking loss, which they found critical to achieving good performance (see [Appendix E.2.4](#) for details).

One shared feature of all the fine-tuned submissions to the sentence-level QE shared task at [WMT 2023](#) is that they are all ensembles of models. Some ensembles consist of multiple versions of the same architecture trained using different data ([Geng et al., 2023](#)), whereas others consist of models utilising different PLMs ([Yan et al., 2023](#)).

[Table 7](#) lists the PLMs used by each model architecture. Although several different PLMs are employed, popular models are versions of [XLM-R](#) which may be due to its size and availability (as it is open source). The majority of PLM used in fine-tuned QE models are encoder-only models with one exception being [mT5](#) used by Google’s [MetricX](#) which is an encoder-decoder model ([Juraska et al., 2023](#)). [Juraska et al. \(2023\)](#) reported that they also experimented with putting a regression head on top of the [mT5](#) encoder and discarding the decoder, but that approach did not result in better performance.

The choice of PLM will affect the size of fine-tuned QE models. [Table 8](#) shows the mean sentence-level performance of the [COMET-KIWI](#) architecture using various PLMs across all language pairs in the test data from the QE shared task at [WMT 2023](#) ([Rei et al., 2023](#)). Although the correlations increase with the size of the PLM, the magnitude of the increase may not always be worth the additional computational cost of the larger models. As discussed in [Shterionov et al. \(2019\)](#), the balance between accuracy and efficiency is an important consideration when using QE models in production. Additionally, several studies have shown that larger models do not consistently outperform their smaller counterparts across all language pairs ([Rei et al., 2023](#); [Guerreiro et al., 2023a](#); [Amrhein et al., 2023](#)).

There has been some research on techniques for reducing model size and inference time without a significant drop in performance for reference-based metrics but not reference-free metrics ([Pu et al., 2021](#); [Rei et al., 2022a](#)).

PLM	Number of Parameters	Spearman Correlation	
		Generic Model	Fine-tuned Model
InfoXLM-L	550M	0.529	-
XLM-R-XL	3.5B	0.537	0.574
XLM-R-XXL	10.7B	0.555	0.575

Table 8: Average [sentence-level](#) correlations across all language pairs in the test data from the [QE](#) shared task at [WMT 2023](#) using [COMET-KIWI](#) architecture with different sized [PLMs](#). The generic models are fine-tuned for the the sentence-level and word-level tasks separately. The table presents the generic and sentence-level fine-tune model results from [Rei et al. \(2023\)](#).

6.5 Training Techniques and Data Augmentation

Although the [fine-tuned QE models](#) listed in [Table 7](#) have different architectures, they all appear to take a similar approach by fine-tuning the [PLM](#) as part of the training process. However, the training differs in some other respects, such as what data is used and how. There are broadly three main categories of training approaches, all of which were compared by the [HW-TSC](#) team behind [CrossQE](#) ([Li et al., 2023](#)) on [DA](#)-scored data:

- Training on authentic QE data
- Training on authentic QE data augmented with synthetic records
- Training on augmented data and then fine-tuning on authentic data

The synthetic data used by HW-TSC contained translations perturbed with deletions, substitutions and insertions and scored using a [reference-based evaluation](#). The three training approaches were applied across four pre-trained models ([COMET-KIWI](#), [XLM-R](#), [InfoXLM](#) and [RemBERT](#)) to create twelve models in total. All except one language pair (English-Marathi) saw little or no benefit when training with the [augmented data](#) compared to only training on the QE data. However, an ensemble of all twelve models was able to outperform each individual model for all language pairs, and the models that were trained with the augmented dataset had a weight of 80%. [Li et al. \(2023\)](#) concluded that the models trained on the augmented dataset could improve the performance of the ensemble and help to prevent overfitting. They also observed that the data augmentation approach might be more successful with more reliable scores; for example, if the synthetic examples had been scored by human annotators rather than by a model.

Other [WMT 2023](#) submissions have also synthetically created example translations with errors. [NJUNLP](#) perturbed [reference](#) translations to create errors of varying severity and computed a corresponding MQM score for each sentence ([Geng et al., 2023](#)). They then used this to pre-train their model before fine-tuning on authentic QE data. Similarly, [Guerreiro et al. \(2023a\)](#) created synthetic [critical error](#) examples using sentences from the MQM dataset. Specifically, they focused on [hallucinations](#) following [Guerreiro et al. \(2023b\)](#), who suggested metrics might perform worse on rare errors because they are not exposed to enough negative examples in their training data. [Juraska et al. \(2023\)](#) also augmented their training data with a small amount of synthetic data that target a [challenge set](#) and found that this can boost the overall performance of their models (keeping the number of synthetic examples to 1–2% of the labelled examples).

[Rei et al. \(2022b\)](#) and [Rei et al. \(2023\)](#) also took a two-step training approach but without relying on synthetic data. First, they trained a generic model using previously released WMT annotated data. They then fine-tuned this model using the 2023 QE data, using different strategies for the [sentence-](#) and [word-level evaluation](#) tasks, even though the architecture was designed for both tasks.

A few additional training strategies are reported in the literature. [Juraska et al. \(2023\)](#) and [Guerreiro et al. \(2023a\)](#) both adopted a strategy of fine-tuning first on DA-scored data and then MQM-scored data. The rationale is that the MQM data are smaller in quantity but the quality of the scores is higher. Additionally, [Juraska et al. \(2023\)](#) found that z -score normalisation of DA scores benefited sentence-level evaluation, but had a detrimental impact on system-level performance. They also found that z -score normalisation did not improve performance when applied to MQM scores.

7 QE Performance

7.1 Overview

QE systems are evaluated on how well they correlate with human quality annotations. The choice of evaluation metric will depend on the QE task. A pairwise ranking accuracy is often used to evaluate system-level QE which rewards correctly ordered scores per system ([Freitag et al., 2023](#); [Deutsch et al., 2023](#)). Pearson, Spearman and Kendall correlations are all used for sentence-level QE ([Freitag et al., 2023](#); [Blain et al., 2023](#)); however, these three correlations will reflect different aspects of performance. For example, the Pearson correlation will capture the linear relationship between the predictions and ground truth scores, whereas Kendall correlation will reward correct ranking decisions. The [Matthew's correlation coefficient \(MCC\)](#) is often used to evaluate word-level QE ([Zerva et al., 2022a](#); [Blain et al., 2023](#)). Other metrics, such as the [mean squared error \(MSE\)](#), may be used for analysis but rarely provide the main assessment of a QE system.

The WMT QE subtask has changed the main evaluation criteria for [sentence-level evaluation](#) from Pearson to Spearman correlation in 2022. That, in addition to changing the evaluated language pairs and updating test datasets each year, makes comparing QE model performance across years difficult. [Appendix F](#) gives an overview of publicly available versions of three generations of models in the [COMET](#) family evaluated on the same data.

This section reviews [SOTA](#) performance of QE systems across a number of categories, primarily focusing on results from WMT 2023. QE metrics have become competitive with and even, in some scenarios, have an advantage over reference-based metrics, which evaluate translations by comparing them against a human generated gold-standard reference translation. Nevertheless, their performance remains highly variable across language pairs. QE systems are also trained on data drawn from a limited number of domains and this can impact performance when tested on out-of-domain data. Lastly, there has been some work on sensitivity of QE systems to [critical errors](#) and [hallucinations](#) showing variability in performance across metrics although the experiments do not always use the latest SOTA systems.

7.2 QE as a Metric

A number of papers have found that QE metrics are competitive with [reference-based](#) metrics and can even outperform them in some scenarios ([Amrhein et al., 2022, 2023](#); [Avramidis and Macketanz, 2022](#); [Freitag et al., 2023](#)). In the WMT 2023 metrics task the highest ranked metric was reference-based (xCOMET-Ensemble) but three QE metrics were in joint second place: xCOMET-QE-Ensemble, [MetricX-23-QE](#) and [GEMBA-MQM](#) (see [Table 9](#)). The WMT 2023 metrics task noted that the [reference-free](#) QE approaches are particularly competitive when the human-generated [references](#) have quality issues ([Freitag et al., 2023](#)).¹⁹

¹⁹Notably, at WMT 2023 some of the Chinese-English human generated reference translations were scored as lower quality than many of the MT system outputs.

Metric Name	Category	Rank	Average Correlation	Citation
xCOMET-Ensemble	fine-tuned	1	0.825	Guerreiro et al. (2023a)
xCOMET-QE-Ensemble	fine-tuned	2	0.808	Guerreiro et al. (2023a)
MetricX-23	fine-tuned	2	0.808	Juraska et al. (2023)
GEMBA-MQM	LLM prompt-based	2	0.802	Kocmi and Federmann (2023b)
<u>MetricX-23-QE</u>	fine-tuned	2	0.800	Juraska et al. (2023)
mbr-metricx-qe	fine-tuned	3	0.788	Naskar et al. (2023)
MaTESe	fine-tuned	3	0.782	Perrella et al. (2022)
<u>COMET-KIWI</u>	fine-tuned	3	0.782	Rei et al. (2022b)
<u>COMET</u>	fine-tuned	3	0.779	Rei et al. (2020a)
<u>BLEURT-20</u>	fine-tuned	3	0.776	Sellam et al. (2020)
KG-BERTScore	embedding similarity	3	0.774	Wu et al. (2023b)
sesscoreX	fine-tuned	3	0.772	Xu et al. (2022)

Table 9: Results of the the top 3 ranked metrics from the metrics shared task at WMT 2023 Freitag et al. (2023), the average correlation is a weighted average over ten different tasks. QE metrics in **bold** and baseline metrics are underlined.

Team	Model	MQM				DA					Citation
		Multi	En-De	Zh-En	He-En	En-Mr	En-Hi	En-Ta	En-Te	En-Gu	
Unbabel-IST	COMET-KIWI	0.594	0.456	0.493	0.668	0.704	0.598	0.739	0.388	0.714	Rei et al. (2023)
IOL Research	-	0.556	0.483	0.482	0.575	0.505	0.600	0.740	0.376	0.695	Yan et al. (2023)
BASELINE	COMET-QE	0.372	0.340	0.447	0.475	0.392	0.281	0.507	0.193	0.337	
HW-TSC	CrossQE	-	0.437	0.460	-	0.692	0.644	0.775	0.394	0.691	Li et al. (2023)
NJUNLP	-	-	0.479	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	Geng et al. (2023)

Table 10: The Spearman correlations from sentence-level QE shared task at WMT 2023; only the baseline and top performing submissions have been provided. The QE model names are provided if they are known, and all the submissions were ensembles of models. The results marked in **bold** correspond to the winning submissions, as they are not significantly outperformed by any other system according to the Williams Significance Test (Williams, 1959). Adapted from Blain et al. (2023)

Traditionally, reference-based metrics, such as BLEU or chrF, do not consider the source text and are based entirely on the target and reference translations. Modern metrics, such as COMET, frequently do take the source as input, meaning they have access to the same information as QE metrics as well as the additional information contained in the reference. Nevertheless, Amrhein et al. (2022) observed reference-based metrics can make errors not exhibited by QE metrics. They concluded that this is because they do not give enough weight to information contained in the source. For example, several metrics showed gender bias, scoring translations with stereotypically feminine or masculine occupation names as higher quality even when the opposite gender was clearly indicated in the source text but not in the reference, which was left ambiguous.²⁰ This conclusion was repeated when evaluating 2023 metrics with the exception of xCOMET-ENSEMBLE (Amrhein et al., 2023). They suggested this might be because the metric is trained for both reference-based and reference-free evaluation.

²⁰The example used in Amrhein et al. (2022) is the German source sentence “Der Manager feuerte die Bäckerin [feminine]”, which contains a profession noun that is clearly marked for gender. The ambiguous reference translation is “The manager fired the baker” whereas the correct and incorrect target translations are “The manager fired the female baker” and “The manager fired the male baker” respectively.

Team	Model	Multi	MQM			Post-Editing		Citation
			En-De	Zh-En	He-En	En-Mr	En-Fa	
Unbabel-IST	COMET-KIWI	0.329	0.246	0.302	0.402	0.347	0.345	Rei et al. (2023)
IOL Research	-	0.298	0.256	0.250	0.359	0.334	0.351	Yan et al. (2023)
BASELINE	-	0.252	0.179	0.225	0.275	0.287	0.293	
NJUNLP	-	-	0.297	-	-	-	-	Geng et al. (2023)

Table 11: The MCC from the word-level QE shared task at WMT 2023; only the baseline and top performing submissions have been provided. The results marked in **bold** correspond to the winning submissions, as they are not significantly outperformed by any other system according to the Williams Significance Test (Williams, 1959). Adapted from Blain et al. (2023)

7.3 Language Pairs

The results from the word- and sentence-level evaluation tasks at the QE shared task at WMT 2023 are shown in Tables 10 and 11. The sentence-level ground truth scores were obtained using either the MQM or DA schemes, and there were eight language pairs in the test set. No training data were provided for Hebrew-English. The performance of the top submissions are shown by language pair as well as for the multilingual task.

The results show that the evaluated QE models do not perform consistently across language pairs. The top Spearman correlations for sentence-level evaluation for each language pair range from 0.394 to 0.775 for DA and from 0.479 to 0.668 for MQM. For word-level evaluation the MCC scores range from 0.297 to 0.402 (Blain et al., 2023).

Previous WMT conferences have reported better performance for language-pairs with a balanced distribution of scores in the training data relative to skewed scores (Specia et al., 2021; Zerva et al., 2022a). For example, in the QE shared task at WMT 2021, English-German and English-Chinese were particularly challenging to predict. The organisers speculate this may be due to less variability in the scores for language pairs where an MT system generally performs well (Specia et al., 2021). The 2021 QE task also noted that language pairs with high correlations (such as Romanian-English and Nepali-English) contained a number of very low quality sentences and the correlations may have been influenced by these outliers (Specia et al., 2021).²¹

The DA sentence-level results show that a larger QE training dataset for a particular language pair does not guarantee a performance boost. English-Marathi has 27,000 records of training data, significantly more than the 7,000 records for the other language pairs scored with the DA scheme (see Table 5). However, the highest correlation for sentence-level evaluation for the English-Marathi test data was 0.704 while English-Tamil and English-Gujarati had correlations of 0.775 and 0.714 respectively.

The word-level task in particular appears to remain challenging with overall low scores. However, only four teams participated in the word-level task and only two of those participated across all five language pairs.

7.4 Zero Shot

The results from the QE shared task at WMT 2023 in Tables 10 and 11 show that performance on the zero-shot language pair Hebrew-English was relatively high for both word- and sentence-level

²¹In the QE shared task at WMT 2021, the Pearson correlation was used for sentence-level evaluation which is more sensitive to outliers than Spearman correlation. As the top performing QE systems in 2021 were generally able to identify the lowest quality text the high correlations that were reported for Romanian-English and Nepali-English are possibly influenced by the existence of the outliers.

evaluation. However, findings of WMT 2022 acknowledged that zero-shot performance seemed dependent on whether the **PLM** used in the submissions had been trained on the **source** and **target** languages of the evaluated language pairs (Zerva et al., 2022a). The wide range of correlations across all language pairs in the 2023 results similarly suggests that the zero-shot predictions might not be as successful if a different language pair had been held out during training.

In a separate study, Sharami et al. (2023) trained a **XLM-R**-based QE model on an English-Italian dataset, which they then tested on four language pairs that had not been exposed to the model while fine-tuning with QE data. The correlation was 0.701 for Romanian-English, which was significantly higher than for English-German (0.308), English-Chinese (0.166) and Russian-English (0.399). The authors speculated the result was due to Italian and Romanian being from the same family of ‘romance languages’.

7.5 Domains

Fine-tuned QE models are likely to be domain-dependent as they are trained on a limited set of data and might be unaware of terminology occurring outside the training domain(s) (Kocyigit et al., 2022). Text data can range from highly technical to very informal language. However, there are not many studies that investigate the robustness of **QE** systems across domains. One reason for this may be that the distinction between domains is not as well-defined as, for example, the distinction between language pairs.

The metrics shared task at **WMT 2021** analysed performance of **reference-based** and QE systems, including **COMET-QE**, on an out-of-domain test set (Freitag et al., 2021b). The task used news content for the in-domain training dataset and translations of TED talks for the out-of-domain dataset. The results showed that **COMET-QE** performance varied by domain across the language pairs. The findings concluded that most metrics (both **reference-based** and **reference-free**) were not robust to a change in domain. However, there have been major developments in QE metrics since **COMET-QE** was developed in 2020, including in the **COMET** family (see Appendix E.2.2) that have not been evaluated on robustness to domain change.

7.6 Sensitivity to Critical Errors

The ability for a **QE** system to identify translations with **critical errors**, or **MAPs**, is important for many use cases. However, the correlations in **Tables 10** and **11** only give a high-level view of performance of QE models, and do not provide any insight on their ability to recognise critical errors specifically.²² Owing to the importance of critical errors, a number of studies analyse performance of QE systems using **challenge sets**, which use automated or manual means to create synthetic examples of critical errors (see **Section 5.3**). Specifically, the QE systems are evaluated on whether they score translations with critical errors as lower than correct translations and whether this depends on the type of error.

Several papers have evaluated, among others, **COMET-KIWI** and **KG-BERTScore** on their sensitivity to critical errors (Alves et al., 2022; Avramidis and Macketanz, 2022; Amrhein et al., 2022, 2023). Each of these studies evaluated different language pairs and used different error taxonomies. Nevertheless, both Alves et al. (2022) and Amrhein and Sennrich (2022) found **KG-BERTScore** to have the best overall performance in terms of its sensitivity to critical errors. Similarly, Amrhein et al. (2023) concluded that both **KG-BERTScore** and **COMET-KIWI** have the best overall performance. Additionally, they reported that relative to the 2022 **COMET-KIWI** model, **COMET-KIWI-XL** is slightly worse and **COMET-KIWI-XXL** performs about the same.

²²The most commonly used version of the **MQM** scoring scheme at **WMT** also scores **critical errors** the same as major errors, see **Appendix B.1**.

[Avramidis and Macketanz \(2022\)](#) found that on average all evaluated metrics performed best on [negation errors](#) and the worst on [named entity errors](#). Correspondingly, [Alves et al. \(2022\)](#) found COMET-KIWI struggled with named entity and [number errors](#). However, [xCOMET](#), one of the latest iterations of the COMET framework, was shown to be sensitive to negation, named entity and number errors ([Guerreiro et al., 2023a](#)).

Decoder-only [LLM prompt-based QE models](#) might perform differently to models that use an encoder-only [PLM](#). For example, [Kocmi and Federmann \(2023b\)](#) found that [GEMBA-MQM](#) was susceptible to falsely assigning [locale convention errors](#) to translations. An example they provided was when the use of the currency Euros was identified as an error in a sentence translated from Czech into English even though the translation was correct. In this case, the error appears to have been incorrectly identified because Euros are not used in the Czech Republic. The authors found that removing the need to identify locale convention errors from the prompt improved the performance of GEMBA-MQM and concluded that further work would be required to improve [GPT](#)'s identification of locale errors.

7.7 Sensitivity to Hallucinations

A number of recent papers have investigated sensitivity of [QE](#) and reference-based metrics to [hallucinations](#) ([Guerreiro et al., 2023b](#); [Dale et al., 2023](#)). They also compared them to a number of [glass-box QE](#) uncertainty-based approaches such as using sequence log-probability output by the [MT](#) system. Both papers concluded that glass-box QE approaches perform really well on this task and outperform [COMET-QE](#). However, neither evaluated more modern QE metrics. [Dale et al. \(2023\)](#) further found that glass-box QE uncertainty-based approaches outperform other methods particularly on [low-resource](#) language pairs. In contrast, all methods do well in detecting hallucinations in text from [high-resource](#) language pairs.

In contrast, the QE shared task at [WMT 2023](#) investigated sensitivity of the submitted [SOTA](#) models to hallucinations ([Blain et al., 2023](#)).²³ The results showed that the best performing QE systems achieved high values of [AUROC](#) and recall across language pairs, and the submission from IOL Research obtained a perfect score for English-German (a high-resource language pair) ([Yan et al., 2023](#)). However, the findings noted that even some of the overall high performing models missed a number of egregious examples. [Oscillatory hallucinations](#) in particular proved difficult to identify. They suggested that this may be because the samples were out-of-distribution of the training data. The conclusions recommended [augmenting](#) the training data with examples of hallucinations.

8 Alternative QE Tasks

8.1 Overview

One disadvantage of standard [sentence-level QE](#) systems is that they generate a single statistic. The scores can be used to rank translations from best to worst but it is harder to determine why a score was given and what it means. This section reviews alternative formulations of the QE task that are more interpretable and so better suited to applied contexts.

As discussed in [Section 3.4](#), some types of errors are more serious than others. This can be in general, such as errors that alter the meaning of the source, but it can also be context dependent. Such errors are commonly labeled as [critical errors](#). Consequently, it might be useful to frame QE as a

²³The organiser created an evaluation dataset consisting of all the samples where the hallucinations had been detected and also samples where the ground truth quality score was above the 25th percentile - this ensured that the other samples did not contain other types of [critical errors](#).

binary critical error classification task. Classifying sentences by whether they contain a critical error or not has a clear application potential as one could triage translations with critical errors for human review.

Alternatively, [explainable QE](#) is defined in terms of [word-level](#) predictions that identify if and where an error has occurred. Some iterations of this task, referred to as fine-grained error prediction, additionally ask for a severity label for the identified errors. In both cases, the word-level labels should help explain the overall sentence-level quality score. This distinguishes these tasks from word-level QE which gives binary ‘OK’ or ‘BAD’ labels that are not associated with a sentence-level assessment. Nevertheless, these tasks could be considered complementary. As discussed below, explainable QE is still a largely underdeveloped area of research and has only been part of [WMT](#) in the last couple of years (2022 and 2023) with very few submissions to the task.

8.2 Critical Error Detection (CED)

[Zhou et al. \(2020\)](#) have argued that framing [QE](#) as a binary classification task, predicting ‘GOOD’ and ‘BAD’ labels, is preferable to framing it as a regression task in applied contexts. A binary label is more interpretable than a quality score when the goal is to decide whether the translation needs to be sent for a review and a [post-edit](#). Additionally, [Zhou et al. \(2020\)](#) argued that binary classification metrics, such as precision or recall, are more interpretable compared to a Pearson or Spearman correlation for evaluating QE model performance.

While the definition of ‘GOOD’ is context dependant, there are certain types of errors that are always considered ‘BAD’, irrespective of the use case. Correspondingly, the QE shared task at [WMT 2021](#) held a sub-task on [CED](#) ([Specia et al., 2021](#)). Participants developed models that output a binary [sentence-level](#) label indicating whether a translation contains a [critical error](#). The data were authentic examples of [MT](#) errors labeled as belonging to one of five categories of critical error; introduction of toxicity (hate, violence or profanity), deviations that may bring a risk to the reader, [sentiment reversal](#) and mistranslations of [named entities](#) and [numbers](#). The language pairs differed in what percentage of data were critical errors.

Model performance by language pair roughly followed skew in the data. That is, the highest [MCC](#) (0.546) was reported for English-German, which had the highest percentage of critical error examples (28%) while the lowest performance was reported for English-Japanese which only had 9% of critical error examples in the data.

8.3 Explainable QE

An explainable [QE](#) task was introduced by [Fomicheva et al. \(2021\)](#). The aim of the task is to train model to output a [sentence-level](#) quality score as well as continuous [word-level](#) labels indicating the likelihood (0–1) of the word being an error. The word-level label can be interpreted as the likelihood the word is part of the rationale for the given score. To create the dataset, human annotators identified erroneous [tokens](#) in sentences they did not give a perfect [DA](#) score to. This was done for both the [source](#) and [target](#) sentences to capture [omission errors](#) as well as [hallucinations](#) or any other mistranslation errors. It is common to distinguish between constrained and unconstrained explainable QE tasks. The constrained task does not allow training models with word-level quality labels whereas the unconstrained task allows word-level training.

There was a lot of variation in the submissions reported by [Fomicheva et al. \(2021\)](#) but all relied on multi-lingual [transformer-based PLMs](#). The results found that the sentence-level score correlation was not predictive of the ability of the model to detect tokens that were identified as part of the rationale behind the score. The authors speculated that this is due to the variety of approaches taken for calculating the sentence-level score. The task was also repeated at the [WMT 2022 QE](#) shared task;

however, only three teams participated in the task (compared to 11 in the core QE tasks), and those teams did not participate across all the available language pairs (Zerva et al., 2022a). The lack of participation in this sub-task meant that there were few general findings on explainable QE. The organisers also noted the need for an improved baseline model for this task, as their baseline model was outperformed by a randomised model for several of the language pairs.

8.4 Fine-grained Error Prediction

The explainable QE task was re-framed at WMT 2023. In this new version, the aim was to predict the error span (start and end token indices) rather than give word-level labels (Blain et al., 2023). Additionally, participants were asked to predict the error severity (major or minor). In effect, the models were trained to re-create MQM style annotations. Two language pairs featured in the annotated training data (English-German and Chinese-English) and an additional language pair was used in the test dataset (Hebrew-English). The organisers used COMET-KIWI as a baseline.

Overall, four teams participated in the task, and the submissions can be split into three approaches.

- Re-purpose an existing word-level model and treat consecutive ‘BAD’ labelled words as an error span.
- Train a model specifically for the task.
- Use GPT-4, prompting it to act as an expert annotator.

Two of the teams used the first approach. One of those teams trained the model to also output error severity while the other (NJUNLP) decided severity based on the ‘OK’ probability being below some threshold value.

The Unbabel-IST team built xCOMET specifically for the task. They created pseudo-references using translations from large MT systems such as DeepL or Google Translate. As the pseudo-reference may contain translation errors, it is first assessed using standard sentence-level QE. If the score is less than 0.5, then xCOMET is run in reference-free mode; otherwise, it is run with the pseudo-reference in reference-based mode.

The Unbabel-IST team also experimented with a GPT-4 prompt-based model, but found that it did not outperform xCOMET. Another team made a submission using a GPT-4 prompting approach but was outperformed by other models. However, the potential advantage of a LLM prompt-based QE model is that a chain-of-thought (CoT) prompting strategy (Wei et al., 2023) can be applied to mimic MQM span annotations. This is the approach taken by GEMBA-MQM, which was successful in the metrics shared task at WMT 2023; however GEMBA-MQM was not used in a submission to this explainable QE task.

The NJUNLP team ranked first for the English-German pair while the xCOMET submission ranked first for the other language pairs, as shown in Table 12. A key observation in the findings was that most teams had higher recall scores compared to precision. The findings also highlighted that the top two submissions, particularly NJUNLP, outputted a higher proportion of ‘MAJOR’ relative to ‘MINOR’ error labels. The lower ranked teams output a more balanced proportion of labels that is closer to what was in the data.

Team	Multi	MQM		
		En-De	Zh-En	He-En
Unbabel-IST	0.220	0.273	0.288	0.279
BASELINE	0.156	0.167	0.219	0.227
NJUNLP	-	0.284	-	-

Table 12: The F1-scores from the error span detection [QE](#) shared task at [WMT 2023](#); only the baseline and top performing submissions have been provided. The results marked in **bold** correspond to the winning submissions, as they are not significantly outperformed by any other system according to the Williams Significance Test ([Williams, 1959](#)). Adapted from [Blain et al. \(2023\)](#)

9 Uncertainty Quantification

9.1 Overview

Both [reference-free evaluation](#) and [reference-based evaluation](#) methods typically output a single value. [Uncertainty-aware MT evaluation](#) aims to also estimate uncertainty of the point prediction, which can be a useful decision support tool. Moreover, one of the papers reviewed in this section demonstrates how predictions of uncertainty could be applied to the generalisation of models to new domains ([Zhan et al., 2023](#)).

Two different sources of uncertainty are often identified in the literature. [Aleatoric uncertainty](#) is due to the noise present in the observed data - for [MT](#), this may be caused by inaccurate or inconsistent ground truth quality scores from human annotators or low quality or inconsistent [reference](#) translations. By contrast, [epistemic uncertainty](#) is due to a lack of knowledge by the model which could arise because of limited training data, such as a lack of domain diversity. Epistemic uncertainty is, in theory, reducible given infinite amounts of training data and an appropriate model.

This section reviews applications of uncertainty quantification for MT evaluation such as [sentence-level evaluation](#), differentiating between epistemic and aleatoric uncertainty and exploiting uncertainty in domain adaptation. Methods for uncertainty quantification and evaluation techniques are detailed in [Appendix G](#) as they are not specific to translation evaluation. Most studies to date have focused on reference-based so we review these as well given uncertainty-aware [QE](#) is less well explored.

9.2 Sentence-level Evaluation

Two [uncertainty-aware](#) methods for [sentence-level evaluation](#) are compared by [Glushkova et al. \(2021\)](#): [Monte Carlo dropout](#) and [deep ensembles](#). Similarly, [Zerva et al. \(2022b\)](#) compare Monte Carlo dropout and deep ensemble methods with [heteroscedastic regression](#), [Kullback-Leibler \(KL\) divergence minimisation](#), [heteroscedastic Monte Carlo dropout](#) and [direct uncertainty prediction \(DUP\)](#). Both papers use the [reference-based COMET](#) as the underlying evaluation model, but the methods could be applied to [reference-free evaluation](#). They both also compare the uncertainty-aware models to a simple constant uncertainty baseline using a Gaussian distribution with the mean matched to the point estimates and a fixed variance across all predictions.

One desirable feature of uncertainty-aware models is that their ability to make point predictions should not be worse than a similar model without uncertainty ([Glushkova et al., 2021](#)). The point predictions made by the uncertainty-aware models used by [Glushkova et al. \(2021\)](#) produced comparable Pearson correlations to the baseline model across nine language pairs. Similarly, [Zerva et al. \(2022b\)](#) found similar correlations for all methods. This indicates that the uncertainty-aware models' ability to make point predictions was not inhibited. In fact, for some language pairs and scoring

systems, the deep ensemble approach in [Zerva et al. \(2022b\)](#) made noticeable improvements on the baseline model's performance.

When the predictive distributions were compared, the uncertainty-aware models used by [Clushkova et al. \(2021\)](#) were better calibrated and produced tighter uncertainty intervals than the baseline model across all the language pairs. However, the baseline produced a better negative log-likelihood score for two of the language pairs. In [Zerva et al. \(2022b\)](#) the heteroscedastic regression, KL divergence minimisation and DUP produced significantly better uncertainty estimates than Monte Carlo dropout and deep ensembles.

More recently, [Zerva and Martins \(2023\)](#) concluded that in the context of reference-based MT evaluation most of the methods discussed above frequently produce misleading confidence intervals that are unrealistically narrow.²⁴ They recommend using [conformal prediction](#) instead and showed it yields the desired marginal coverage level, such as a 90% predictive interval indicating that the true value is contained inside the interval at least 90% of the time. They additionally analysed coverage conditional on a number of data attributes such as language pair or the translation quality level and showed that it varies by attribute group and can be below the desired threshold for some of them. Consequently, they recommend computing conformal predictive intervals separately for the different attribute groups, such as by language pair. Similarly, [Giovannotti \(2023\)](#) demonstrated that conformal prediction applied to [QE](#) provides good coverage and can outperform the standard fixed variance Gaussian baseline.²⁵

With the emergence of prompting-based LLM approaches to QE, entirely different approaches to uncertainty estimation might be required as natural language generation poses unique challenges ([Kuhn et al., 2023](#)).

9.3 Predicting Aleatoric and Epistemic Uncertainty

[Zerva et al. \(2022b\)](#) considered the strengths and weaknesses of various [uncertainty-aware](#) methods for translation evaluation and, in particular, how they represent [aleatoric](#) and [epistemic uncertainty](#). They observed that [heteroscedastic regression](#) is suitable for expressing aleatoric uncertainty as it models the variance from the training data. A disadvantage of this approach is that each sample in the training dataset requires either multiple ground-truth quality scores from different annotators or, in the case of [reference-based evaluation](#), multiple [reference](#) translations.

By contrast, [Zerva et al. \(2022b\)](#) identified [Monte Carlo dropout](#) and [deep ensembles](#) as methods that conflate aleatoric and epistemic uncertainty. Both these approaches represent uncertainty by making predictions with multiple versions of a model and then calculating the mean and variance of the predicted values. While these approaches may capture uncertainty from noise in the data (aleatoric uncertainty) and uncertainty owing to a lack of training data (which contributes to epistemic uncertainty), they fail to make any assessment about epistemic uncertainty arising from the underlying model. Model uncertainty can be understood as a form of bias and might be particularly relevant when using a model to score out-of-distribution samples ([Hüllermeier and Waegeman, 2021](#)). [Zerva et al. \(2022b\)](#) also noted that Monte Carlo dropout and deep ensembles have the disadvantage of being computationally expensive - Monte Carlo dropout at inference time and deep ensembles at training time.

DUP is an uncertainty aware approach introduced by [Lahlou et al. \(2023\)](#) that can also model the epistemic model uncertainty. The two-step method first trains a standard regression model and then a second model (using a distinct training dataset) to predict the generalisation error of the first

²⁴[Zerva and Martins \(2023\)](#) used COMET as the underlying model.

²⁵[Giovannotti \(2023\)](#) trained their own XLM-R based QE model, rather than using an already trained benchmark model such as COMET-KIWI, and they used a different non-conformity measure to [Zerva and Martins \(2023\)](#) (see [Appendix C](#)).

model. [Lahlou et al. \(2023\)](#) demonstrated that this approach captures the aleatoric uncertainty and the epistemic uncertainty due to lack of training data *and* model bias.²⁶ One disadvantage of the approach is that it requires two distinct training datasets; however, [Zerva et al. \(2022b\)](#) compared the computational time taken for training and inference with DUP and found it to have much lower cost than Monte Carlo dropout and deep ensembles.

[Zerva et al. \(2022b\)](#) observed that methods capable of recognising epistemic uncertainty should produce larger uncertainty values on out-of-domain test data, than on test data from the same domain as the training data. They trained the reference-based evaluation model [COMET](#) on data from the news domain as a base model (using data from [WMT 2017–2020](#)) and evaluated the various uncertainty-aware methods using two test sets. One test set consisted of data from the news domain and the other of data gathered from TED talks. The TED talk data were out-of-domain compared to the training dataset.

The uncertainty values were averaged over each test set and language pair. The results showed that heteroscedastic regression had the same average uncertainty scores for both data domains for each language pair. This result was expected, as the method only models aleatoric uncertainty. By contrast, Monte Carlo dropout and deep ensembles had a higher average uncertainty value on the in-domain data than out-of-domain data, apart from the deep ensemble model on the English-German language pair. This result demonstrated that Monte Carlo dropout and deep ensembles might not satisfactorily capture epistemic uncertainty or be suitable for identifying out-of-domain samples.

The DUP method produced higher uncertainty values for the out-of-domain data than the in-domain data for two of the tested language pairs (English-German and English-Russian) but not the third (Chinese-English). [Zerva et al. \(2022b\)](#) noted that in the case of the Chinese-English test data, the aleatoric uncertainty was more than twice as high across the test datasets than the other language pairs (which they observed from the output of heteroscedastic regression), and they suggested this may affect the results when attempting to measure epistemic uncertainty.

[Zerva et al. \(2022b\)](#) only conducted experiments using reference-based evaluation models although the key finding that the most appropriate method for estimating uncertainty will depend on the use case is likely to still be relevant to [QE](#). Heteroscedastic regression and DUP appear to be promising methods for understanding aleatoric and total uncertainty; however, results of DUP on the Chinese-English data suggest this should be treated with caution.

9.4 Domain Adaptation

[Zhan et al. \(2023\)](#) investigated using [test-time adaptation](#) ([Liang et al., 2023](#)), which relies on uncertainty estimates, to improve the generalisation of a model on an out-of-distribution dataset. Test-time adaptation updates a limited number of model parameters using a test dataset; however, it does this without using the ground-truth scores. Instead of optimising the neural network using a loss function estimating the difference between the point prediction and the ground truth, the authors implemented an optimisation objective to minimise the uncertainty of the predictions (estimated using [Monte Carlo dropout](#)).

The approach was applied to data from the [WMT 2021 metrics shared task](#). The data comprised of three language pairs (English-German, Chinese-English and English-Russian) with records from news sources and TED talks. The records from the TED talks were out-of-domain; that is, they were not seen by the models during training. The authors used [COMET-QE](#) as a reference-free model.

²⁶The approach taken by [Lahlou et al. \(2023\)](#) subtracted an estimate of aleatoric uncertainty from the predicted uncertainty value to obtain just the epistemic uncertainty and called the approach the direct *epistemic* uncertainty prediction. However, [Zerva et al. \(2022b\)](#) did not subtract the aleatoric uncertainty from their prediction and therefore amended the name to the direct uncertainty prediction.

The model with test-time adaptation was able to outperform the model without adaptation for two of the three language pairs on the out-of-domain dataset. The system-level Pearson correlation increased from 0.694 to 0.829 for English-German and from -0.208 to 0.257 for Chinese-English. However, the correlation for English-Russian did not increase, in fact it decreased slightly from 0.817 to 0.807.

10 Conclusions

10.1 Overview

This report has reviewed recent developments in [QE](#) for [MT](#). [Section 3](#) showed that MT errors can alter the meaning of translations, even though they may be rare. This motivates the requirement to assess the quality of translations, particularly in use cases where the impact of an incorrect translation can be significant. The attraction of QE approaches is that they can be conducted at run-time, at scale, without the need for a gold-standard [reference](#) translation.

This section summarises conclusions drawn from the review. It then outlines some practical considerations for using QE models in practice.

10.2 Defining and Measuring Quality

Measuring translation quality is a complex and subjective task. It requires considering whether the translation is grammatically correct and whether it preserves the original meaning and perhaps even style and tone. Which quality dimensions are important can also depend on the particular use case and domain such as [UGC](#), professional communications and scientific or literary texts.

The complexity of the task is reflected in inconsistencies across scoring schemes and individual annotators. The literature offers guidelines for reaching annotator consensus such as providing full document context or relying on professional translators and it is common practice to derive a single ground-truth score. On the other hand, [Basile et al. \(2021\)](#) have suggested that a more appropriate approach to handling annotator disagreement in [NLP](#) tasks might be to incorporate it into modelling and evaluation.

There are a number of translation quality annotation schemes. The [MQM](#) framework and [post-edits](#) have an advantage over [DA](#) as their granularity means they can be used for a number of different [QE](#) tasks such as [word-level evaluation](#), [sentence-level evaluation](#) and error span detection. As many top-performing supervised models at the QE shared task at WMT 2023 were [multi-task](#) (trained to output both word-level tags and [sentence-level](#) scores) it may be beneficial to curate any new datasets using one of these approaches.

10.3 QE Data

The majority of [QE](#) data are curated by [WMT](#), who release new datasets each year. Most of the data are annotated with [DA](#), [MQM](#) or [post-edits](#). There are also a number of datasets with [sentence-level](#) binary labels indicating whether they contain [critical errors](#) or [hallucinations](#).

It is conceivable that post-edited data might already be collected in some organisations that are interested in implementing QE, particularly if there is a work-flow where human linguists correct machine generated translations. If such data exist, then they could be used to create an in-house QE dataset.

As errors generated by MT systems can be rare, [challenge sets](#) are also used to evaluate MT systems or to augment training data where applicable. The challenge sets described in [Section 5.3](#) mostly comprise of synthetic data. There is a risk that the errors they contain are not representative

of an MT system that is to be evaluated and the assigned error categories might not correspond to the use case. Like the authentic QE datasets, the challenge sets are limited by language pairs. However, the [SMAUG framework](#) (Alves et al., 2022) could be used to create a novel synthetic dataset for a specific application.

10.4 Trends in QE

The majority of QE model submissions at WMT 2023 were ensembles of [black-box](#), [multi-task](#) models that fine-tune an encoder-only PLM. A currently dominant family of models includes [COMET-KIWI](#) (Rei et al., 2023), versions of which are often used to benchmark other models. As well as being used in high performing submissions at WMT the popularity of the [COMET](#) models may be due to the fact they have been released on HuggingFace (see [Appendix H](#) for links to these and other models).

In 2023, [fine-tuned QE model](#) development primarily focused on scaling up existing models. However, it is not clear that the computational cost is worth the performance boost and the largest models can be outperformed by smaller models in some circumstances (Blain et al., 2023).

Another trend for fine-tuned QE models is to explore various approaches to pre-training and augmenting QE datasets with synthetic data. In particular, the generation of synthetic data is targeted at creating more errors than would naturally occur from a [SOTA MT](#) system. The quantity of synthetic data does not necessarily have to be large in order to be effective; one particular result described in [Section 6.5](#) found that a targeted synthetic dataset 1–2% of the size of the authentic dataset was most effective (Juraska et al., 2023).

Only one of the high-performing models at the WMT 2023 metrics shared task (listed in [Table 7](#)) used a prompt-based approach with a decoder-only LLM. An advantage of this approach is that it does not require large amounts of training data as the LLM is not fine-tuned. Given the current popularity of LLMs, these approaches may become more dominant in future iterations of WMT.

The lack of submissions from models that use [glass-box](#) features does not necessarily mean these approaches are obsolete. Glass-box QE approaches could justify further investigation if QE was to be implemented in a production environment with a glass-box MT system.

10.5 Performance

WMT 2023 showed that QE models can be competitive with the top performing [reference-based](#) metrics (Freitag et al., 2023) and that performance could significantly vary by language pair (Blain et al., 2023). Additionally, more QE training data for a particular language pair do not guarantee better performance and there were promising results for zero-shot language pairs (as shown in [Tables 10](#) and [11](#)). It is likely that the performance is also influenced by the training data of the underlying PLM (rather than just the QE training data), which will have been exposed to varying quantities of the [source](#) and [target](#) languages (Zerva et al., 2022a).

The performance of QE models can vary when faced with different types of [critical errors](#) and [hallucinations](#). Several studies showed that some error types, such as [named entity errors](#), [number errors](#) and [oscillatory hallucinations](#), are harder to identify than others (Avramidis and Macketanz, 2022; Alves et al., 2022; Blain et al., 2023). These findings could be informative if targeted synthetic datasets are curated for fine-tuning QE models.

There does not appear to be any recent research that considers how well QE models generalise across domains. Such insight could be useful if implementing a QE system in a production environment as it could influence how much authentic data should be gathered and annotated for training (if applicable) and evaluating the QE system.

10.6 Explainability and Uncertainty

The typical [QE sentence-level evaluation](#) task provides a single score to represent quality. However, this may not be sufficient information for a human to make a judgement about the text. [Sections 8 and 9](#) considered several under-explored formulations of QE aimed at producing output that might be more informative for an end-user.

Firstly, in recent years, various forms of [explainable QE](#) have been sub-tasks of the [WMT QE](#) shared task, from producing [sentence-level](#) binary labels indicating presence of a [critical error](#) to identifying error spans with severity labels in text ([Specia et al., 2021](#); [Zerva et al., 2022a](#); [Blain et al., 2023](#)). However, these have received relatively few submissions and the task was formulated differently in each year.

Secondly, [uncertainty-aware MT evaluation](#) considers methods to estimate a predictive uncertainty interval rather than a point prediction. The majority of findings reported in the literature relate to [reference-based evaluation](#) although they could also be applied in a [QE](#) setting. In particular, uncertainty-aware methods might be useful for identifying out-of-domain samples or adapting models to unseen domains ([Zhan et al., 2023](#)).

10.7 Practical Considerations

There are a number of key considerations when deploying [QE](#) models in production. To begin with, each specific use case has different data requirements to fine-tune (if applicable) and evaluate QE systems. Some of these will depend on answers to the following questions:

- How is quality defined (e.g., what constitutes a major or a [critical error](#))?
- Is the desired output a numerical score, a binary label or explainable annotations?
- What are the language pairs and text domains of interest?

The use case might also influence what annotation scheme is the most appropriate or feasible. The annotation process should ideally involve multiple professional translator and wherever possible, the evaluation data should be authentic examples obtained from the same [MT](#) system(s) that will be used in the production environment.

In terms of implementing an in-house QE system, a model such as [COMET-KIWI](#) might be a reasonable starting point for [sentence-](#) or [word-level](#) QE. This is because of its generally high-performance and accessibility. The performance boost of the larger [COMET-KIWI](#) models seems limited relative to the increased compute cost. Smaller sized models might be preferable and sufficient for many real world applications ([Shterionov et al., 2019](#)). If the required output is different to what [COMET-KIWI](#) provides, alternative architectures may need to be investigated. Moreover, if the QE model could have access to some other output from the MT system, then [glass-box QE](#) might be of interest, especially as they might offer better trade-off between accuracy and efficiency ([Specia et al., 2020a](#)).

Acronyms

- ACES** Translation Accuracy Challenge Set. [39](#)
- AUROC** area under the receiver operating characteristic curve. [28](#)
- BERT** Bidirectional Encoder Representations from Transformers. [6](#), [49](#), [54](#), [55](#), [57](#)
- BERTScore** BERT Score. [14](#), [49](#), [57](#)
- BLEU** BiLingual Evaluation Understudy. [14](#), [25](#), [49](#), [50](#), [58](#)
- CED** critical error detection. [17](#), [18](#), [29](#), [63](#)
- chrF** character n -gram F-score. [14](#), [25](#), [49](#)
- COMET** Crosslingual Optimized Metric for Evaluation of Translation. [14](#), [24](#), [25](#), [27](#), [28](#), [31–33](#), [35](#), [39](#), [43](#), [49](#), [50](#), [54–57](#), [59](#), [60](#)
- CoT** chain-of-thought. [30](#), [58](#)
- DA+SQM** direct assessment + scalar quality metric. [11](#), [13](#)
- DA** direct assessment. [11](#), [13–16](#), [23](#), [24](#), [26](#), [29](#), [34](#), [40](#), [51](#), [52](#), [58](#), [59](#), [63](#)
- DUP** direct uncertainty prediction. [31–33](#), [61](#)
- EAPrompt** error analysis prompting. [58](#)
- ECE** expected calibration error. [62](#)
- EU** European Union. [8](#)
- GEMBA** GPT Estimation Metric Based Assessment. [58](#), [64](#)
- GPT** Generative Pre-trained Transformer. [19](#), [21](#), [28](#), [30](#), [58](#)
- HTER** human-mediated translation edit rate. [11](#)
- HW-TSC** Huawei Translation Services Center. [19](#), [23](#), [41](#), [56](#)
- IID** independent and identically distributed. [39](#), [61](#)
- IST** Instituto Superior Técnico. [43](#), [55](#)
- KG** knowledge graph. [57](#)
- KL** Kullback-Leibler. [31](#), [41](#), [60](#)
- KNN** k -nearest neighbour. [61](#)
- LLM** large language model. [5–7](#), [20](#), [21](#), [32](#), [35](#), [40](#), [41](#), [53](#), [58](#)
- LSTM** Long Short Term Memory. [54](#)

MAP meaning-altering perturbation. 9, 18, 27, 49

MCC Matthew's correlation coefficient. 24, 26, 29

METEOR Metric for Evaluation of Translation with Explicit word Ordering. 49, 52, 58

MLQE-PE Multilingual Quality Estimation and Post-Editing Dataset. 15, 63

MPP meaning-preserving perturbation. 9, 49

MQM multidimensional quality metric. 11–16, 18, 23, 24, 26, 27, 30, 34, 40, 45–48, 50, 55, 58, 63

MSE mean squared error. 24, 56

MT machine translation. 5–11, 13–15, 17, 18, 20, 21, 24, 26, 28–32, 34–36, 39–43, 49–52, 55, 56, 58, 61

NER named entity recognition. 57

NJU Nanjing University. 41

NLP natural language processing. 13, 34

NMT neural machine translation. 10

NN neural network. 20, 49, 51, 52, 60

PE post-edit. 16

PLM pre-trained language model. 5, 6, 14, 19–23, 27–29, 35, 40, 49, 51–57

PPS predictive Pearson score. 62

QE quality estimation. 5–7, 10, 14–36, 39–43, 51–58, 63

QEFV quality estimation feature vector. 53

RNN recurrent neural network. 20, 53, 54

SMAUG Sentence-level Multilingual AUGmentation. 42

SOTA state-of-the-art. 5–7, 21, 24, 28, 35, 51

SQM scalar quality metric. 11, 13, 63

SVM support vector machine. 20

TER translation edit rate. 49

UGC user-generated content. 7, 8, 10, 15, 17, 34

UN United Nations. 8

UPS uncertainty Pearson score. 62

WMT Conference on Machine Translation. 6–11, 13, 15–31, 33–36, 45, 49–59, 63

XLM Cross-lingual Language Model. 54

XLM-R XLM-RoBERTa. 19, 22, 23, 27, 32, 51, 52, 54–57

Glossary

- ACES dataset** a [challenge set](#) for [MT](#) metric evaluation ([Amrhein et al., 2023](#)), see also [ACES](#). 15, 17, 47, 63
- addition error** (of the output of an [MT](#) system) when the translation includes words that do not appear in the [source](#) text. 10, 17
- aleatoric uncertainty** uncertainty that is due to the noise present in the observed data. 31–33, 40, 60, 61
- ambiguity error** (of the output of an [MT](#) system) when the translation fails to capture the correct meaning of an ambiguous word, such as when words have multiple meanings. 9
- back-translate** when monolingual text in the [target](#) language is translated into the [source](#) language using a separate, usually smaller, [MT](#) system to synthetically create parallel data for [MT](#) model training. 7, 8, 44
- black-box QE** an approach to [QE](#) where it is assumed that the only information accessible from the [MT](#) system is the generated translation and the details of the [MT](#) system are otherwise treated as unknown. 5, 19–21, 35, 39, 41, 43, 51–53
- candidate translation** a translation from an [MT](#) system, see also [hypothesis translation](#), [target](#). 14, 40
- catastrophic error** (of the output of an [MT](#) system) see [critical error](#). 9
- challenge set** (in the context of [QE](#) evaluation) a dataset curated of specific examples designed to test a metric’s sensitivity to particular types of translation errors. 15, 17, 23, 27, 34, 35, 39–41
- COMET-KIWI** a supervised [black-box multi-task QE model](#) in the [COMET](#) family ([Rei et al., 2022b](#)). 19, 22, 23, 25–28, 30, 32, 35, 36, 55, 56, 58, 59
- COMET-QE** a supervised [black-box QE model](#) in the [COMET](#) family ([Rei et al., 2020b](#)). 25, 27, 28, 55
- conformal prediction** a method for computing uncertainty intervals for new predictions that are guaranteed to contain the true value with a user specified probability under the assumption that the data are [independent and identically distributed \(IID\)](#) ([Shafer and Vovk, 2007](#)). 32, 61
- critical error** (of the output of an [MT](#) system) when the translation does not preserve the meaning of the source text. 5–7, 9, 10, 17, 18, 23, 24, 27–29, 34–36, 39, 40, 45, 48
- CrossQE** a supervised [black-box multi-task QE model](#) ([Li et al., 2023](#)). 25
- data augmentation** when genuine or synthetic data are added to an existing training dataset. 23, 28
- deep ensemble** an ensemble of N neural networks that is each trained separately with a different random initialisation - the output from the ensemble can then be used to generate a distribution for each input record ([Lakshminarayanan et al., 2017](#)). 31–33, 60, 61
- DEMETR dataset** a [challenge set](#) for [MT](#) metric evaluation ([Karpinska et al., 2022](#)). 15, 17, 18, 48, 63

direct assessment a scheme for scoring the quality of translated text using a scale of 0-100. 11, 13–16, 23, 24, 26, 29, 34, 37, 40, 51, 52, 58, 59, 63

direct uncertainty prediction a two-step method to estimate total uncertainty (aleatoric uncertainty and epistemic uncertainty) (Lahlou et al., 2023). 31–33, 37, 61

domain generalisation the aim of creating a model (such as an MT or QE model) that can perform equally well on a variety of domains, including domains not seen during training. 8

embedding similarity QE model a QE model that uses some PLM to encode the source and target sentences without any additional fine-tuning of the PLM; the prediction of quality is then obtained by comparing the two embeddings. 21

epistemic uncertainty uncertainty due to a lack of knowledge. 31–33, 40, 60, 61

explainable QE an evaluation of a machine translation that provides additional output aimed at explaining the overall sentence-level quality score. 29, 30, 36

fine-tuned QE model a supervised QE model that uses some PLM as a base model and fine-tunes the model on QE data. 6, 21–23, 27, 35, 51

fully detached hallucination (of the output of an MT system) a type of hallucination when the meaning of the translation bears no relation to the source (unlike a strongly detached hallucination). 18, 42

GEMBA-DA a prompt-based LLM model for QE that uses a zero-shot approach to predict a score on the DA scale (Kocmi and Federmann, 2023a). 58

GEMBA-MQM a prompt-based LLM model for QE that uses a three-shot approach to predict a score using the MQM framework (Kocmi and Federmann, 2023b). 19, 24, 28, 30, 58

glass-box QE an approach to QE that makes use of various information from the MT system not limited to just the generated translation. 20, 21, 28, 35, 36, 51

hallucination (of the output of an MT system) a type of critical error when the translation is unfaithful to, or in some way detached, from the source text. 10, 18, 23, 24, 28, 29, 34, 35, 40, 42, 63

HalOmi dataset a challenge set for MT metric evaluation (Dale et al., 2023). 18, 63

heteroscedastic (of data) when the noise in the data does not have constant variance. 60

heteroscedastic Monte Carlo dropout when Monte Carlo dropout is applied to heteroscedastic regression (Kendall and Gal, 2017). 31

heteroscedastic regression a regression task that predicts both a mean and a variance (Le et al., 2005). 31–33, 40, 60, 61

high-resource (of a language pair) when there are large numbers of samples of translations from the source to the target language. 8, 28

hypothesis translation a translation from an MT system, see also candidate translation, target. 14, 39

KG-BERTScore an [system-level QE](#) model that does not require a training phase ([Wu et al., 2023b](#)). [19](#), [21](#), [27](#), [57](#)

KL divergence minimisation an [uncertainty-aware MT evaluation](#) approach that uses the [KL divergence](#) as the loss function and predicts both a mean and variance for each input ([Zerva et al., 2022b](#)). [31](#), [32](#), [60](#), [61](#)

LLM prompt-based QE model a [QE](#) model that uses some pre-trained [LLM](#) as a base model and a prompting strategy to estimate the quality of translations. [21](#), [28](#), [30](#)

locale convention error (of the output of an [MT](#) system) when the translation does not use the locale conventions of the [target](#) language; for example using ‘;’ instead of ‘.’ as the decimal point. [9](#), [28](#)

low-resource (of a language pair) when there are relatively few samples of translations from the [source](#) to the [target](#) language. [8](#), [28](#)

MetricX a family of supervised [black-box QE](#) metrics that can be applied to either [reference-based](#) or [reference-free sentence-level evaluation](#) ([Juraska et al., 2023](#)). [19](#), [22](#), [24](#), [55](#)

Monte Carlo dropout a method for estimating the uncertainty of a neural network by running the model for N forward passes with units of the network dropped at random ([Gal and Ghahramani, 2016](#)). [20](#), [31–33](#), [40](#), [51](#), [52](#), [60](#), [61](#)

MT-TestSuite a [challenge set](#) for [MT](#) and [MT](#) metric evaluation ([Macketanz et al., 2022](#)). [17](#), [63](#)

multi-task QE model a [QE](#) model designed to perform multiple tasks, typically [word-](#) and [sentence-level](#) quality predictions. [21](#), [34](#), [35](#), [39](#), [43](#), [55](#), [56](#)

multidimensional quality metric a scheme for scoring the quality of translated text by identifying error spans and assigning error category and severity to each, with an associated score for each error type from which an overall [sentence-level](#) quality score is calculated. [11–16](#), [18](#), [23](#), [24](#), [26](#), [27](#), [30](#), [34](#), [38](#), [40](#), [45–48](#), [50](#), [55](#), [58](#), [63](#)

n-gram a sequence of n adjacent symbols (letters or words). [14](#), [49](#)

named entity error (of the output of an [MT](#) system) when the translated text includes a mistranslation of a person, organisation or location. [9](#), [10](#), [17](#), [28](#), [29](#), [35](#), [50](#)

negation error (of the output of an [MT](#) system) when the translated text adds or leaves out a negation marker, changing the meaning of a sentence. [28](#), [49](#)

NJUNLP the name of a team from [Nanjing University \(NJU\)](#) and [HW-TSC](#) that developed [QE](#) models ([Geng et al., 2023](#)). [19](#), [23](#), [30](#), [56](#), [63](#)

noun phrase error (of the output of an [MT](#) system) when the translation fails to translate a sequence of nouns, such as “slime mold” or an idiom, correctly. [9](#)

number error (of the output of an [MT](#) system) when a numerical value is not translated correctly. [9](#), [17](#), [28](#), [29](#), [35](#), [50](#)

omission error (of the output of an [MT](#) system) when the translation omits a word that appears in the [source](#) text. [15](#), [17](#), [18](#), [29](#)

OpenKiwi an open-source framework for QE including an implementation of the [predictor-estimator architecture](#) (Kepler et al., 2019b). 53, 55

oscillatory hallucination (of the output of an MT system) a type of [hallucination](#) when the translation contains erroneous repetitions. 18, 28, 35

post-edit the process of editing a translation to correct any mistakes. 6, 7, 15, 16, 29, 34, 38

post-edit ratio a ratio of the number of edits required to correct a translation to the total number of tokens in the text. 11

predictor-estimator architecture a two-stage QE model architecture that uses the predictor model to generate feature vectors that are then used as input to the estimator model. 42, 53, 54

quality estimation an evaluation of a machine translation made without access to a gold-standard [reference](#) translation for comparison, cf. [reference-based evaluation](#). 5–7, 10, 14–36, 38–43, 51–58, 63

reference (of text) a translation considered correct or perfect (usually generated by a human linguist). 5, 6, 13, 14, 20, 21, 23–25, 30–32, 34, 42, 43, 49, 53, 55, 57, 58

reference-based evaluation an evaluation of a translation made by comparing the translated text to some [reference](#) text in the same language (usually generated by a human linguist), can sometimes also consider the [source](#) text in the evaluation process, cf. [quality estimation](#). 14, 20, 21, 23–25, 27, 28, 30–33, 35, 36, 41–43, 54, 55, 57

reference-bias when translations that are superficially similar to the [reference](#) are scored as better than equally good translations that are trivially dissimilar. 14

reference-free evaluation see [quality estimation](#). 6, 14, 24, 25, 27, 30, 31, 33, 41, 43, 55, 57

rephrasing error (of the output of an MT system) when the translation follows the structure of the [source](#) text, but it does not make sense to in the [target](#) language, or when rephrasing is applied but incorrectly. 8

scalar quality metric a scheme for scoring the [sentence-level](#) quality of translated text using an integer value between zero and six. 11, 13, 38, 63

sentence-level evaluation a task that typically aims to predict a single score that represents the quality of a translated sentence. 5–7, 14, 17, 19–26, 28–31, 34, 36, 40–43, 51, 54–58

sentiment reversal error (of the output of an MT system) when the translation expresses the opposite of the intended sentiment. 9, 10, 17, 29

SMAUG framework a framework that deploys automated methods to modify translations to exhibit particular types of translation error (Alves et al., 2022), see also SMAUG. 17, 35, 64

source the language or text to be translated. 5–7, 10, 13–15, 20–22, 25, 27, 29, 35, 39–43, 49, 51–58

strongly detached hallucination (of the output of an MT system) a type of [hallucination](#) when the translation is at least partially related to the source (unlike a [fully detached hallucination](#)). 18, 40

system-level evaluation a task that typically aims to evaluate MT performance over an entire corpus of translations, usually by aggregating sentence-level scores. 14, 19, 21, 41, 55, 57

target the language that a source text is to be translated into, or the text that has been translated in the target language. 5–7, 13–15, 20–22, 25, 27, 29, 35, 39–43, 49, 52–58

test-time adaptation when some parameters of a pre-trained model are updated using unlabelled data during testing. 33, 34, 64

token a short sequence of characters with meaning, typically a word, subword or punctuation character. 11, 29, 30, 45, 52, 55

transformer a deep learning architecture based on the multi-head attention mechanism (Vaswani et al., 2017). 6, 7, 20, 29, 51

translation edit rate an automated metric for reference-based evaluation that measures the amount of editing required to transform a target text into the reference text. 38, 49

Unbabel-IST a team from Unbabel and Instituto Superior Técnico (IST) that have developed QE models (Rei et al., 2023). 19, 30, 51, 55

uncertainty-aware MT evaluation an evaluation of a machine translation that estimates a predictive uncertainty interval around a point-prediction quality score. 31–33, 36, 41, 62

user-generated content (in the context of this literature review) text posted by users online, such as social media posts or product reviews. 7, 8, 10, 15, 17, 34, 38

word-level evaluation typically a binary task which predicts a binary ‘OK’ or ‘BAD’ tag for each word of translated text. 5, 7, 14, 15, 19–24, 26, 29, 30, 34, 36, 41, 54–57

xCOMET a supervised black-box multi-task QE model in the COMET family designed for error span detection that can be applied to either reference-based or reference-free evaluation (Guerreiro et al., 2023a). 19, 24, 25, 28, 30, 55, 56

Appendix A Example Translations

To illustrate the difficulty in scoring translation quality, [Table 13](#) presents example translations in a number of languages. All of these were created with Google Translate, translating the English sentence “Government Retires 15 More Senior Tax Officials On Graft Charges” into the respective language and then back into English.

Of particular interest are translations of the words “retire” and “charges”. A number of the translations use the word “fire” instead of “retire” or “allegations” instead of “charges”. These are both aligned with the overall sentence but have a different meaning. Some annotators might consider these as correct translations and others might consider them wrong.

Additionally, the translations of the term “graft charge” across languages demonstrate varying degrees of errors. The term is correctly translated as “bribery” or “corruption” in some languages. However, in Czech or Tamil the translation does not make sense and in Xhosa the meaning is significantly altered to “Trade Fees”. A nonsensical translation is in some regards less worrying as it is easy to spot.

Language	Back-translation
German	Government fires 15 more senior tax officials over bribery allegations
Chinese	Government retires 15 more senior tax officials over corruption allegations
Russian	The government fred another 15 senior tax officials over bribery charges
Czech	Government to retire 15 more senior tax officials on splitting charges
Gujarati	The government retired 15 more senior tax officials on graft charges
Tamil	Govt retires 15 more senior tax officials on craft charges
Xhosa	Government Retires 15 More Senior Tax Officials Through Trade Fees

Table 13: Example [back-translations](#) in a number of languages of the English sentence “Government Retires 15 More Senior Tax Officials On Graft Charges” using Google Translate. The sentence is taken from the MQM dataset.

Appendix B Translation Error Categories and Severities

B.1 Multidimensional Quality Metric (MQM)

MQM is a general framework that asks annotators to classify errors by category (see [Table 14](#)) and severity (minor, major, **critical**). Each category and severity are assigned weights, which can be adapted to suit the specific use case (this might involve not using all the severity categories).

Error Category	Description
Accuracy	Addition Translation includes information not present in the source.
	Omission Translation is missing content from the source.
	Mistranslation Translation does not accurately represent the source.
	Untranslated text Source text has been left untranslated.
Fluency	Punctuation Incorrect punctuation (for locale or style).
	Spelling Incorrect spelling or capitalization.
	Grammar Problems with grammar, other than orthography.
	Register Wrong grammatical register (e.g., inappropriately informal pronouns).
	Inconsistency Internal inconsistency (not related to terminology).
Terminology	Character encoding Characters are garbled due to incorrect encoding.
	Inappropriate for context Terminology is non-standard or does not fit context.
Style	Inconsistent use Terminology is used inconsistently.
	Awkward Translation has stylistic problems.
Locale convention	Address format Wrong format for addresses.
	Currency format Wrong format for currency.
	Date format Wrong format for dates.
	Name format Wrong format for names.
	Telephone format Wrong format for telephone numbers.
Other	Time format Wrong format for time expressions.
	Any other issues.
Source error	An error in the source.
Non-translation	Impossible to reliably characterize distinct errors.

Table 14: MQM error hierarchy taken from [Freitag et al. \(2021a\)](#).

As described in [Freitag et al. \(2021a,b\)](#), Google’s MQM annotation guidelines consider small imperfections to be minor errors whereas actual translation or grammatical errors are classed as major. Correspondingly, any punctuation errors that change the sentence meaning should be scored as major errors. There is no critical error category and the number of errors is capped at 5 per segment (prioritising the most severe errors). The final score is a sum of the error weights (see [Table 15](#)) and ranges from 0 (the best) to 25 (the worst). This is the most commonly used scheme at [WMT](#).

In Unbabel’s MQM annotation guidelines²⁷ minor errors are described as fluency or stylistic errors that do not lead to a loss of meaning. Any errors that make the text difficult to understand, impacting its usability, are classed as major. Errors that change the meaning of the text are classed as critical. The weighted sum of all errors (see [Table 16](#) for the respective weights), is normalised by segment length (i.e., dividing by the number of [tokens](#)). This value is then subtracted from 1 and multiplied by 100. WMT commonly re-scores data annotated with this scheme to match Google’s approach by relabeling critical errors as major ([Freitag et al., 2022, 2023](#)).

²⁷The annotation guidelines are available on [Unbabel’s website](#).

Severity	Category	Weight
Major	Non-translation	25
	all others	5
Minor	Fluency/Punctuation	0.1
	all others	1
Neutral	all	0

Table 15: Google's MQM error weights.

Severity	Category	Weight
Critical	all	10
Major	all	5
Minor	all	1

Table 16: Unbabel's MQM error weights.

B.2 Translation Accuracy Challenge Set (ACES)

The [ACES dataset](#) uses a taxonomy of translation errors that broadly fall into 10 categories, each with a proposed severity weight inspired by the [MQM](#) framework ([Amrhein et al., 2022](#)). Errors with a weight of 1 are considered minor whereas errors with a weight of 5 are considered major (and punctuation errors are weighted as 0.1) :

1. **Addition:** target includes content not present in the source [weight=5]
2. **Omission:** content in the source is missing from the target translation [weight=5]
3. **Mistranslation:** target changes meaning of the source (e.g., due to change in word order, literal translation of idioms or errors related to numbers, named entities, units and date-time) [weight=5]
4. **Untranslated:** the target contains untranslated source tokens [weight=1]
5. **Do not translate:** content in the source that should have been left untranslated has been translated (e.g., titles of songs) [weight=1]
6. **Over-translation:** target contains a narrower category term (hyponym) than used in the source (e.g., “red” instead of “colour”) [weight=5]
7. **Under-translation:** target contains a broader category term (hypernym) than used in the source (e.g., “animal” instead of “dog”) [weight=5]
8. **Real-world knowledge:** target is sub-optimal given real-world understanding (e.g., the meaning is against common sense, use of hypernym should be scored higher than use of a hyponym, use of synonym should be scored higher than an antonym) [weight=1]
9. **Wrong language:** the target is in the wrong but similar language (e.g., Catalan instead of Spanish) [weight=1]
10. **Punctuation:** deleting or substituting punctuation characters (e.g., commas, which act as boundary markers, quotation marks, which indicate speech, or replacing exclamation points with question marks thus turning a statement into a question) [weight=0.1]

With the exception of punctuation, which is a fluency error, all the categories are considered accuracy errors. Some of the categories, such as ‘mistranslation’, are further divided into subcategories, as illustrated in Figure 1 in [Amrhein et al. \(2022\)](#).

As with the MQM framework, the final ACES-score is a sum of the error weights. The authors note that the proposed weights for each error category are merely suggestions and should not be treated as definitive. It is possible other weighting scheme might be more appropriate.

B.3 Diagnosing Evaluation Metrics for Translation (DEMETR)

The DEMETR dataset (Karpinska et al., 2022) consists of 31 error categories and four baselines (see Table 17). The baseline categories are used to establish lower and upper bounds on metric output as they are assumed to elicit the lowest and highest possible scores. The error classification follows the MQM framework and so each error category has an associated severity label (minor, major, critical).

Error Category	Description	Severity
Accuracy	word repetition (twice)	minor
	word repetition (four times)	minor
	too general word (undertranslation)	major
	untranslated word (codemix)	major
	omitted prepositional phrase	major
	incorrect word added	critical
	change to antonym	critical
	change to negation	critical
	replaced named entity	critical
	incorrect numeric	critical
incorrect gender pronoun	critical	
Fluency	omitted conjunction	minor
	part of speech shift	minor
	switched word order (word swap)	minor
	incorrect case (pronouns)	minor
	incorrect preposition or article	minor-major
	incorrect tense	major
	incorrect aspect	major
change to interrogative	major	
Mixed	omitted adj/adv	minor-major
	omitted content verb	critical
	omitted noun	critical
	omitted subject	critical
Typography	omitted named entity	critical
	misspelled word	minor
	deleted character	minor
	omitted final punctuation	minor
	added punctuation	minor
	tokenized sentence	minor
	lowercase sentence	minor
first word lowercase	minor	
Baseline	empty string	base
	unrelated translation	base
	shuffled words	base
	reference as translation	base

Table 17: List of error categories and associated severity labels from Karpinska et al. (2022).

Appendix C Reference-based Evaluation Metrics

Automated MT evaluation metrics score MT output, referred to as the **target**, by comparing it against **reference** translations. They can be broadly divided into edit distance, string matching, embedding based or learned. All categories of metrics are still commonly used in the literature.

C.1 Edit Distance

Edit distance is the amount of editing a human would have to do for a **target** translation to be acceptable (Snover et al., 2006). Specifically, **translation edit rate (TER)** is the minimum number of edits (e.g., word insertions, deletions, substitutions or shifts) needed to change the target to match the closest reference translation.²⁸

A disadvantage is that all edits have equal cost. This means punctuation or mis-capitalization edits are treated the same as shifts or substitutions of words. Grammatically correct translations that use the same words as the reference but in a different order will be penalised. This is also true for use of synonyms or paraphrasing.

C.2 String Matching

A large number of MT evaluation metrics measure lexical similarity by counting **n-gram** matches between the **target** and **reference** translations and computing precision or F statistics. The two most prevalent metrics in this category are **BLEU** (Papineni et al., 2002), where the n-gram matches are computed at the word level, and **chrF** (Popović, 2015), where the n-grams are character level.

A key issue with these metrics is that they penalize paraphrasing and use of synonyms. This is somewhat addressed by **METEOR**, another word-level n-gram matching metric, that counts exact matches as well as matches after the words are stemmed and matching on synonyms (Lavie and Agarwal, 2007).

None of the string matching metrics can reliably distinguish errors of different severity (i.e., **MPPs** from **MAPs**). For example, a translation that omits a **negation** (e.g., “not”) is penalized the same as a translation that omits indefinite or definite articles (i.e., “a”, “the”).

C.3 Embedding Based

More recently, researchers have made use of **PLMs** in MT evaluation. For example, **BERTScore** uses **BERT** to transform the **target** and **reference** into contextual embeddings and then computes cosine similarity between the embeddings (Zhang et al., 2020). Zhang et al. (2020) showed **BERTScore** is more robust to paraphrased translations than **n-gram** matching metrics like **BLEU**.

C.4 Learned

The latest trend in MT evaluation is to combine **PLMs** with **NNs** trained for the task. For example, **COMET** is a learned MT evaluation framework (Rei et al., 2020a) that is consistently one of the top ranked metrics in the **WMT** metrics task (Freitag et al., 2022).

The COMET framework consists of a cross-lingual encoder (e.g., **BERT**) followed by a NN trained to output a quality score. The COMET model performs better when the **source** sentence is included in the input compared to when the model is only exposed to the **target** and **reference** sentences as is common for MT evaluation metrics (Rei et al., 2020a).

²⁸There is a variant of edit distance computed at character level Wang et al. (2016) as well as edit distance that allows for reordering of blocks of words at a constant cost Leusch et al. (2006). However, these variants are not commonly used.

WMT 2022 metrics task concluded that such learned metrics significantly outperform string matching metrics like BLEU (Freitag et al., 2022). Specifically, learned metrics show overall better correlations with human ratings on MQM scored data and consistently perform better on text from different domains (news, social, e-commerce and chat data). Nevertheless, COMET struggles with certain types of MT errors such as named entity and number errors (Alves et al., 2022; Amrhein and Sennrich, 2022).

Appendix D Glass-box QE Models

This Appendix covers some of the main developments in [glass-box QE](#) models. Broadly, these models use features derived from the underlying [MT](#) system, such as uncertainty, to estimate quality. This can be done by performing direct calculations with the MT uncertainty or by training supervised QE models with these features as input.

D.1 Glass-box QE (2020)

[Fomicheva et al. \(2020b\)](#) investigated three groups of [QE](#) metrics based exclusively on information extracted from the underlying [transformer](#)-based [MT](#) model. The first group used the softmax output distribution of the MT model. The second group applied [Monte Carlo dropout](#) ([Gal and Ghahramani, 2016](#)) to the MT model, which requires the MT model to generate multiple translations for each [source](#) text, with some model parameters perturbed each time. The third group used the attention weights from each head and each layer of the decoder.

[Fomicheva et al. \(2020b\)](#) applied all metrics from the three groups to [DA](#) scored data. The Monte Carlo dropout based metrics achieved the highest correlations with human judgements for all tested language pairs. Moreover, the correlations were competitive with supervised approaches that were [SOTA](#) at the time of publication.

The two highest performing Monte Carlo dropout metrics were submitted to the [QE](#) shared task at [WMT 2020](#) ([Fomicheva et al., 2020a](#)). The best performance across both metrics by language pair is reported as a single submission in [Table 18](#) under the team name of Bergamot-LATTE-GB. The Bergamot-LATTE-GB submission performed better than the [WMT](#) baseline, but was outperformed by other models. This included a supervised [black-box QE](#) model submitted by the same team also shown in [Table 18](#) as Bergamot-LATTE-BB. However, a benefit of the glass-box Monte Carlo dropout approaches is that they do not require training data.

D.2 Supervised Glass-box QE (2020)

The [glass-box](#) features described in [Section D.1](#) were also used as input to a supervised [QE](#) model by [Fomicheva et al. \(2020a\)](#) and submitted to the [QE](#) shared task at [WMT 2020](#). [Fomicheva et al. \(2020a\)](#) experimented with random forest ([Ho, 1995](#)) and [XG-Boost](#) ([Chen and Guestrin, 2016](#)) regression algorithms that did not take any additional [black-box](#) features as input. The best results from these trained models on the test data are shown in [Table 18](#) under the submission name of Bergamot. This supervised model outperformed the Bergamot-LATTE-GB approach described in the previous section.

[Moura et al. \(2020\)](#) also experimented with using glass-box features at [WMT 2020](#). Specifically, they submitted two models, both [NNs](#) using [XLM-R](#) as the base. One of the models (named [Unbabel-IST-BB](#) in [Table 18](#)) used only black-box features, whereas the other ([Unbabel-IST-BB-GB](#)) used a combination of black-box and glass-box features as input. In contrast to the Bergamot results, the [Unbabel-IST-BB-GB](#) submission outperformed its purely black-box counterpart.

All the approaches described were outperformed by a supervised black-box [QE](#) model called [TransQuest](#) (see [Appendix E.2.1](#)). However, the [WMT 2020](#) organisers noted that glass-box approaches may result in a favourable trade-off between accuracy and efficiency ([Specia et al., 2020a](#)).

D.3 QEMind (2021 - 2022)

[Wang et al. \(2021a\)](#) developed a model called [QEMind](#) for [sentence-level evaluation](#) using the [DA](#) scoring scheme. It is a [fine-tuned QE model](#) that uses [XLM-R](#) as the base [PLM](#). The architecture of

Submission Name	Supervised Submission	Features		Si-En	Ne-En	Et-En	Ro-En	En-De	En-Zh	Ru-En	Multi	Citation
		Black-box	Glass-box									
TransQuest	✓	✓		0.68	0.82	0.82	0.91	0.55	0.54	0.81	0.72	Ranasinghe et al. (2020b)
Bergamot-LATTE-BB	✓	✓		0.68	0.81	0.83	0.91	0.54	0.53	0.80	0.72	Fomicheva et al. (2020a)
Unbabel-IST-BB-GB	✓	✓	✓	0.64	0.79	0.77	0.89	0.52	0.49	0.77	0.67	Moura et al. (2020)
Bergamot	✓		✓	0.56	0.66	0.68	0.8	0.48	0.43	-	-	Fomicheva et al. (2020a)
Bergamot-LATTE-GB			✓	0.51	0.60	0.64	0.69	0.26	0.32	-	0.49	Fomicheva et al. (2020a)
Unbabel-IST-BB	✓	✓		0.56	0.60	0.69	0.71	0.27	0.35	-	0.58	Moura et al. (2020)
BASELINE	✓	✓		0.37	0.39	0.48	0.68	0.15	0.19	0.55	0.38	Specia et al. (2020a)

Table 18: The Pearson correlation of the submissions to the sentence-level QE shared task at WMT 2020. Only the top performing model is shown along with the models described in Appendix D.1 and D.2. The results marked in **bold** correspond to the winning submissions, as they are not significantly outperformed by any other system according to the Williams Significance Test (Williams, 1959). Adapted from Specia et al. (2020a)

the model shares similarities with black-box QE models as the [source](#) and [target](#) text are fed into the PLM and the output (which, in the case of QEMind, is the [CLS] token) becomes the input of a feed-forward NN. However, inspired by the work of Fomicheva et al. (2020b), QEMind also used uncertainty features obtained from the MT system as input to the feed-forward NN.

Three different sets of features relating to uncertainty were used by Wang et al. (2021a). The first set of features uses the decoding probabilities from each step of the output from the MT model, such as their standard deviation. The second set is obtained by applying Monte Carlo dropout to the MT model and evaluating similarity of the Monte Carlo-sampled outputs using the METEOR metric. The third set of features are created by first adding noise to the source text by replacing words with alternatives generated using another XLM-R model and then scoring these on similarity using the METEOR metric.

QEMind was used as a submission to the QE shared task at WMT 2021 and 2022. In 2021, it was the highest performing submission over multiple languages (Specia et al., 2021) and Wang et al. (2021a) showed in their experiments that the model that utilised 3 uncertainty features outperformed versions of the model without these features. In 2022, QEMind was only submitted to language pairs scored using the DA scoring scheme and was outperformed in all but one of the language pairs.

Appendix E Black-box QE Models

This Appendix covers some of the main methodological developments in [black-box QE](#) models, such as the introduction of the [predictor-estimator architecture](#), the application of [PLMs](#) and, more recently, [LLMs](#). Within this chronology, specific frameworks and models are presented to outline varying approaches to QE in recent years - the models were selected as they appear in studies reviewed in the report.

E.1 Predictor-Estimator Architecture

The two-stage [predictor-estimator QE](#) model was proposed by [Kim et al. \(2017a\)](#) (see [Figure 2](#)). The predictor model acts as a pre-task to QE and is trained on a large parallel corpora of [source](#) and [reference](#) translation texts to predict a randomly masked word in the reference translation. The authors assumed that the model should correctly predict the missing word if the reference translation is good quality. Conversely, if the translation is poor quality, then the prediction will be much harder. The predictor used by [Kim et al. \(2017a\)](#) was a bidirectional, bilingual [RNN](#) language model.

Figure 2: A representation of the two stages of the [predictor-estimator architecture](#) making a prediction of translation quality, adapted from [Kim et al. \(2017a\)](#)

The predictor model is then applied to QE training data with every word in the target text masked in turn to generate a feature vector, called a [quality estimation feature vector \(QEFV\)](#), for each word. The QEFVs and ground-truth quality scores are then used to train the estimator neural network to predict the quality scores.

The advantage over previous methods for QE is that the feature vectors are not manually designed - they are generated through the prediction task. This potentially allows for more complex relationships to be represented as the predictor acts as a feature extractor.

The predictor-estimator architecture was used in the highest-ranked submission to the [QE](#) shared task at [WMT 2017](#) ([Kim et al., 2017b](#)). The architecture is implemented in [OpenKiwi](#), an open-source framework for QE ([Kepler et al., 2019b](#)).

E.2 PLMs for QE (2019)

The QE shared task at WMT 2019 saw many, but not all, submissions rely on PLMs. One approach, taken by Kepler et al. (2019a), was to maintain the predictor-estimator architecture, but to replace the predictor model with a PLM; the following models were considered for the predictor component:

- A RNN-based model using Long Short Term Memory (LSTM) nodes
- A transformer encoder
- BERT
- Cross-lingual Language Model (XLM)

The model with the XLM predictor outperformed the others for word-level and sentence-level QE tasks. However, the authors also experimented with ensembles of models and found these to demonstrate superior performance, outperforming all the individual QE models. The submissions by Kepler et al. (2019a) achieved the best results across the two QE tasks it was entered in and across all language pairs at WMT 2019.

E.2.1 TransQuest Framework (2020)

TransQuest is an open-source framework for sentence-level QE (Ranasinghe et al., 2020a). The framework uses XLM-R and implements two different architectures for sentence-level QE predictions:

- **MonoTransQuest** - Uses one XLM-R model with the source and target sentences concatenated to form a single input (with a separator token in between).
- **SiameseTransQuest** - Uses two XLM-R models with the source and target sentences fed into separate models.

To compute a quality score, MonoTransQuest uses softmax as the last layer. The SiameseTransQuest model computes cosine similarity between the source and target sentence representations outputted by the two XLM-R models.

For both architectures, the authors experimented with pooling strategies for the output of the transformer models. MonoTransQuest uses the [CLS] token embedding as it contains a representation of the entire sequence. Early experiments showed it lead to better results than other strategies. For SiameseTransQuest, computing the mean of all the embeddings outputted by each XLM-R model was the most promising pooling strategy.

TransQuest was submitted to the sentence-level QE shared task at WMT 2020 (Ranasinghe et al., 2020b). An ensemble version of MonoTransQuest trained with data augmentation was one of two submissions at WMT 2020 that had the highest Pearson correlation for all languages in the sentence-level QE task. The results comfortably outperformed the baseline results for all language pairs.

E.2.2 COMET Framework (2020-2023)

COMET is a framework initially developed by Unbabel²⁹ for reference-based evaluation (Rei et al., 2020a). It has since been adapted for sentence-level QE by training the model with only the source

²⁹<https://unbabel.com/>

and [target](#) as inputs, the so-called [COMET-QE](#) model ([Rei et al., 2020b, 2021](#)), and gone through a number of additional developments described below.

The core COMET model consists of a cross-lingual encoder (e.g., [BERT](#)) composed of several transformer encoder layers and a pooling layer that aggregates information from all the encoder layers into a single embedding per token. This was motivated by past observations that the different layers can capture linguistic information that is relevant for different downstream tasks. When used for reference-based evaluation, the framework was found to perform better when the source sentence is also included in the model input (compared to when the model is only exposed to the target and [reference](#) sentences as is common for [MT](#) evaluation metrics).

Unbabel together with the [IST](#) at University of Lisbon combined the COMET and [OpenKiwi](#) frameworks to develop [COMET-KIWI](#) ([Rei et al., 2022b](#)). The architecture produces two outputs simultaneously, making it a [multi-task QE model](#). The first is a [sentence-level](#) score prediction, and the second is [word-level](#) output, providing a binary ‘OK’ or ‘BAD’ tag for each word. [Rei et al. \(2022b\)](#) found training the two tasks jointly led to a performance boost, particularly for the sentence-level prediction. COMET-KIWI achieved very competitive results across the QE shared task at [WMT 2022](#). In particular, it achieved the highest correlation for multilingual QE at sentence- and word-level as well for the majority of individual language pairs. The final submission used an ensemble of models.

For WMT 2023, [IST-Unbabel](#) focused primarily on scaling up the COMET-KIWI model in terms of model size and training data ([Rei et al., 2023](#)). They employed [XLM-R](#) XL and XXL ([Conneau et al., 2020](#)) as the pre-trained encoders and name the resulting models COMET-KIWI-XL and COMET-KIWI-XXL.

Additionally, the team developed a variation of the model called [xCOMET](#), of which there are also XL and XXL variants. The model can be applied to either reference-based or [reference-free evaluation](#) and is also a multi-task model, producing a sentence-level score and more fine-grained word-level output indicating error severity of ‘OK’, ‘MINOR’, ‘MAJOR’ or ‘CRITICAL’. The additional granularity of the word outputs enables error span prediction and means that an [MQM](#) score can be inferred. The final sentence-level score is a weighted sum of the sentence-level prediction and the [MQM](#) score computed from the word-level tags.

E.2.3 MetricX (2022 - 2023)

[MetricX](#) is a learned regression-based model architecture developed by Google for both [reference-based](#) and [reference-free](#) that was submitted to the metrics shared task at [WMT 2022](#) and [2023](#) ([Juraska et al., 2023](#)). The [MetricX](#) family of models makes predictions at [sentence-level](#) only (which can be aggregated to achieve [system-level](#) scores) and incorporates two architectures based on alternative [PLMs](#). The first uses [mT5](#) ([Xue et al., 2021](#)), an encoder-decoder model, which encodes the [source](#) and [target](#) sentences and generates a distribution over the vocabulary for each token in each sentence. It then uses an arbitrary index in the vocabulary distribution for the first generated [token](#) (i.e., the first decoding step) to represent the predicted score. The model is then fine-tuned using [QE](#) data (in the case of reference-free predictions). This approach was found to work better than putting a regression head on top of the encoder and discarding the decoder.

The second architecture uses the pre-trained [PaLM 2 Bison](#) model ([Anil et al., 2023](#)). A regression layer is added to the top of the input encoding and is then trained on [QE](#) data. For reference-free evaluation, the two architectures showed comparable sentence-level performance; however, the approach that used [PaLM 2 Bison](#) outperformed the [mT5](#) model when system-level performance was evaluated ([Juraska et al., 2023](#)).

E.2.4 NJUNLP (2022 - 2023)

NJUNLP is a team from Nanjing University (NJU) and HW-TSC that submitted models to the QE shared task at WMT 2022 and 2023 (Geng et al., 2022, 2023). The submissions used XLM-R (Conneau et al., 2020) as backbone and fine-tuned the model using QE data. Similarly to the COMET-KIWI and xCOMET models, the NJUNLP team developed a multi-task QE model to produce both word- and sentence-level scores.

The NJUNLP model adopts a margin rank loss, defined as:

$$L_{\text{Rank}} = \max(0, -r(\hat{m}^i - \hat{m}^j) + \epsilon) \quad (1)$$

where \hat{m}^i and \hat{m}^j denote the output scores of the i^{th} and j^{th} translations from the current batch, r denotes the rank label ($r = 1$ if $m^i > m^j$, $r = -1$ if $m^i < m^j$ where m^i and m^j are the ground-truth scores) and ϵ is some small margin. The rank loss captures the ordinal relations between translations which is particularly important for tasks such as selecting the best translation from different MT systems.

To train the model on both tasks, the margin rank loss function is combined with the sentence-level MSE loss function (L_{MSE}) and the word-level cross-entropy loss (L_{CE}) to create a QE loss function for some parameters α and β :

$$L_{\text{QE}} = L_{\text{CE}} + \alpha L_{\text{MSE}} + \beta L_{\text{Rank}} \quad (2)$$

The loss functions differentiates it from the COMET models, which use a weighted sum of the MSE and cross-entropy loss functions. Geng et al. (2022) demonstrated that the inclusion of the margin rank loss improved the performance of their model, compared to only using cross-entropy and MSE.

E.2.5 CrossQE (2022 - 2023)

The CrossQE model architecture was developed by HW-TSC for both word- and sentence-level QE tasks (Tao et al., 2022; Li et al., 2023). The approach uses a pre-trained base model, f_{base} , to generate embeddings of the source and target sentences, s and t , concatenated in both orders³⁰: $[s, t]$ and $[t, s]$. The embedding sequences are processed by an average pooling layer to obtain two vector representations for each of the source and target sentences. The features are then extended using their absolute difference and element-wise multiplication. The feature vectors are then concatenated and input into a regression head to predict a final score.

Li et al. (2023) compared the use of XLM-R (Conneau et al., 2020), InfoXLM (Chi et al., 2021), RemBERT Chung et al. (2021) and COMET-KIWI (Rei et al., 2022b) as base models. The results showed that COMET-KIWI achieved the highest sentence-level correlation, although it was outperformed by an ensemble of all the models.

E.2.6 IOL Research (2023)

The IOL Research team at Transn³¹ experimented with creating models for both word- and sentence-level QE tasks (Yan et al., 2023). Similar to many of the other discussed approaches, IOL Research developed an architecture that uses a PLM to encode the source and target sentences. They found that creating a multi-task QE model (that output both word tags and sentence-level scores) improved

³⁰In related work, Eo et al. (2021) found that the order of the source and target sentences in the input to a PLM-based model influenced the performance of the model.

³¹<https://www.transn.com/en/>

the performance of the sentence-level task, but only benefited one language pair in the word-level task.

Yan et al. (2023) also experimented with different PLMs as base models, similarly to the team behind CrossQE (Li et al., 2023), and found that mDeBERTa (He et al., 2021) provided the best performance for sentence-level evaluation. The performance by PLM for word-level evaluation was more varied, with none of the PLMs consistently outperforming the others. Ensembles of the architecture that combined different PLMs could outperform each individual model for both tasks.

E.2.7 KG-BERTScore (2022 - 2023)

Wu et al. (2023b) proposed a [system-level QE](#) metric called [KG-BERTScore](#) whereby a score is generated using a multilingual [knowledge graph \(KG\)](#) combined with an adaptation of the [reference-based BERTScore](#) metric.

BERTScore uses [BERT](#) to transform the [target](#) and [reference](#) translations into contextual embeddings and then computes cosine similarity between the embeddings as a measure of quality (Zhang et al., 2020). KG-BERTScore adapts [BERTScore](#) for [reference-free evaluation](#) by comparing the target and the [source](#) text. As in the original metric, it first generates word embeddings using a pre-trained multilingual model (Wu et al. (2023b) used [XLM-R](#) rather than BERT) creating a sequence of vectors representing the source sentence, $\mathbf{x} = \langle \mathbf{x}_1, \dots, \mathbf{x}_i, \dots, \mathbf{x}_n \rangle$, and the target sentence, $\hat{\mathbf{x}} = \langle \hat{\mathbf{x}}_1, \dots, \hat{\mathbf{x}}_j, \dots, \hat{\mathbf{x}}_m \rangle$. The sentence-level F_{BERT_k} score is then defined as follows for the k^{th} pair of sentences:

$$R = \frac{1}{|\mathbf{x}|} \sum_{\mathbf{x}_i \in \mathbf{x}} \max_{\hat{\mathbf{x}}_j \in \hat{\mathbf{x}}} \mathbf{x}_i^T \hat{\mathbf{x}}_j \quad (3)$$

$$P = \frac{1}{|\hat{\mathbf{x}}|} \sum_{\hat{\mathbf{x}}_j \in \hat{\mathbf{x}}} \max_{\mathbf{x}_i \in \mathbf{x}} \hat{\mathbf{x}}_j^T \mathbf{x}_i \quad (4)$$

$$F_{\text{BERT}_k} = 2 \frac{P \cdot R}{P + R} \quad (5)$$

A system-level F_{BERT} score can then be defined as the mean of F_{BERT_k} over all sentence pairs. In their 2023 submission to the [WMT](#) metrics task, the team used [COMET-QE](#) to calculate BERTScore (Wu et al., 2023a).

The second component of the metric uses a [named entity recognition \(NER\)](#) model to identify named entities in the source and target sentences and retrieving their entity IDs in a multilingual knowledge graph. If the same named entity appears in both the source and target language, then it will have the same entity ID. For a source sentence, s_k , and a target sentence, t_k , the knowledge graph score is defined as the number of matching entities between the source and target sentences, divided by the number of entities in the source sentence:

$$F_{\text{KG}_k} = \frac{\text{matches}(\text{entities}(s_k), \text{entities}(t_k))}{|\text{entities}(s_k)|} \quad (6)$$

The F_{BERT_k} and F_{KG_k} scores are then combined using a hyperparameter α , where $0 < \alpha < 1$, to calculate the [KG-BERTScore](#) for the k^{th} sentence:

$$F_{\text{KG-BERT}_k} = \alpha \cdot F_{\text{KG}_k} + (1 - \alpha) \cdot F_{\text{BERT}_k} \quad (7)$$

The system-level $F_{\text{KG-BERT}}$ score is then the mean value of all sentence-level scores for some dataset of N source and target sentence pairs:

$$F_{\text{KG-BERT}} = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{k=1}^N F_{\text{KG-BERT}_k} \quad (8)$$

E.3 LLMs for QE (2023)

Recent developments have seen the application of LLMs to QE tasks, although their use is not dominant. Rei et al. (2023) compared GPT-4 (OpenAI et al., 2023) to an ensemble of COMET-KIWI models for sentence-level QE. They found that ensembles of COMET-KIWI models achieved higher correlations for all language pairs than the GPT-4 model. The authors also found GPT-4 to be very sensitive to the number of examples included in the prompt, their ordering, and the number of errors within each example. They also noted that using a system such as GPT-4 was very expensive and slow compared to other approaches.

However, Rei et al. (2023) did not provide detail about the strategy used for creating the prompts for GPT-4 other than that they generated scores using an MQM framework. It is possible that a different prompting strategy could have led to better and more stable performance.

E.3.1 EAPrompt (2023)

The effectiveness of eliciting MT evaluations (with and without reference translation) from ChatGPT using different prompting strategies was investigated by Lu et al. (2024). The authors describe a ‘standard’ approach to writing prompts for LLMs that is similar to the DA approach, where the LLM is given the source and target texts and is asked to score the target translation (perhaps between 0 and 100) based on its quality.

The authors then introduce an alternative prompting method called error analysis prompting (EAPrompt), which is a CoT prompting strategy (Wei et al., 2023). This provides more human-like reasoning by first asking the LLM to identify major and minor errors in the translation, and then, in a second step, score the translation based on the number of errors. This approach is motivated by the MQM framework. The EAPrompt method outperformed the previous approach.

The authors drew some general conclusions about using ChatGPT for translation evaluation tasks. Firstly, ChatGPT could produce different output and scores when presented with the same information. Secondly, when multiple translations are presented together ChatGPT seemed to score the earlier translations as being higher quality than the later translations. Thirdly, when justifying an evaluation, ChatGPT sometimes referenced an existing metric such as BLEU or METEOR and sometimes appeared to prioritise the BLEU score.

E.3.2 GEMBA (2023)

GEMBA is a family of evaluation metrics created by Microsoft that utilise GPT models (OpenAI et al., 2023). GEMBA-DA uses a zero-shot approach to predict a single score without specifying the scale in detail (Kocmi and Federmann, 2023a). GEMBA-MQM uses a three-shot prompting technique that mimics the approach to creating MQM scores (Kocmi and Federmann, 2023b). GEMBA-MQM was highly ranked in the metrics shared task at WMT 2023. They experimented with different versions of GPT models and found the method only works with GPT-3.5 and larger models. Kocmi and Federmann (2023b) noted that a limitation of the approach is that it relies on proprietary GPT models: the training data for GPT is unknown and the performance has been shown to fluctuate over time (Chen et al., 2023).

Appendix F COMET Models Performance

A number of models in the [COMET](#) family (see Section [E.2.2](#) for description) have been made publicly available on HuggingFace (see Appendix [H.1](#)). The publicly available models are generic versions of the fine-tuned models submitted to [WMT](#). Table [19](#) shows performance of three generations of the publicly released models evaluated on [DA](#) test data from WMT 2023. The generic [COMET-KIWI](#) models' results on the WMT 2023 data have also been reported in [Rei et al. \(2023\)](#).

Model	Year	English-Gujarati	English-Hindi	English-Marathi	English-Tamil	English-Telegu
COMET-QE	2020	0.343	0.283	0.375	0.486	0.245
COMETKiwi	2022	0.577	0.394	0.625	0.549	0.229
COMETKiwi-XL	2023	0.637	0.536	0.664	0.607	0.335

Table 19: Spearman correlations of models in the [COMET](#) family currently available on HuggingFace evaluated on the [WMT 2023 DA](#) test data. Year indicates when the model was released.

Appendix G Estimating Uncertainty

G.1 Methods for Estimating Uncertainty

G.1.1 Monte Carlo Dropout

Monte Carlo dropout (Gal and Ghahramani, 2016) can be used with a single NN-based evaluation system, such as COMET. To make a prediction for some record, the model is first run for N forward passes with units of the network dropped at random with some probability generating N output samples. There are different methods that can then be applied to generate a distribution. A typical approach is to assume the samples have been drawn from a Gaussian - the sample mean and variance can then be used to estimate the distribution parameters. The variance parameter may be used as the uncertainty estimate. The disadvantage of Monte Carlo dropout is the number of forward passes needed to generate a prediction. Also, this approach does not distinguish between aleatoric and epistemic uncertainty.

G.1.2 Deep Ensembles

Deep ensembles require N multiple neural networks, each trained separately with a different random initialisation (Lakshminarayanan et al., 2017). The output of the models is then used to generate a distribution for each input record, as with Monte Carlo dropout.

Compared to Monte Carlo dropout, deep ensembles are usually less convenient as it requires training multiple models. However, the value of N for deep ensembles is typically less than that required for Monte Carlo dropout. Like Monte Carlo dropout, deep ensembles do not distinguish between aleatoric and epistemic uncertainty.

G.1.3 Heteroscedastic Regression

Data are often heteroscedastic; that is, the noise in the data does not have constant variance throughout. Heteroscedastic regression adapts a neural network to output two values in the final layer: a mean and a variance (Le et al., 2005). The loss function is also updated to include the variance.

This approach ensures that the mean and variance are learned as a function of the data - thus representing aleatoric uncertainty. This is in contrast to Monte Carlo dropout and deep ensembles, which make their estimates based on model variance.

G.1.4 KL Divergence Minimisation

The KL divergence is a measure of how different one probability distribution is from another. Similar to heteroscedastic regression, KL divergence minimisation models the estimated score using a mean and variance; however, as a ground truth it also models the scores from multiple annotators using a mean and variance Zerva et al. (2022b). A formulation of the KL divergence for Gaussian distributions is then used in the loss function for the model.

As with the heteroscedastic regression, the KL divergence minimisation learns about the uncertainty of the output through the data and is therefore representing aleatoric uncertainty.

G.1.5 Heteroscedastic Monte Carlo Dropout

Given a method for modelling aleatoric uncertainty, such as heteroscedastic regression, Monte Carlo dropout can then be applied to obtain a set $Q = \{\hat{q}_1, \dots, \hat{q}_M\}$ of predicted scores and a set $\Sigma = \{\hat{\sigma}_1^2, \dots, \hat{\sigma}_M^2\}$ of variance estimates. The sample variance of Q can be used as an estimator of

epistemic uncertainty, and the sample mean of Σ can be used as an estimator of aleatoric uncertainty (Kendall and Gal, 2017). The sum of the two uncertainties can then be used as an estimate of the total uncertainty over the M samples:

$$\hat{U}_{\text{total}} = \frac{1}{M} \sum_{j=1}^M \hat{q}_j^2 - \left(\frac{1}{M} \sum_{j=1}^M \hat{q}_j \right)^2 + \frac{1}{M} \sum_{j=1}^M \hat{\sigma}_j^2 \quad (9)$$

This approach is not limited to heteroscedastic regression. Other methods to estimate the score and variance, such as KL divergence minimisation could be applied. Similarly, deep ensembles could be used instead of Monte Carlo dropout.

G.1.6 Direct Uncertainty Prediction

A two-step method to estimate total uncertainty (aleatoric uncertainty and epistemic uncertainty) called DUP was presented in Lahlou et al. (2023). The first step uses an evaluation model, \mathcal{M}_Q , to generate the quality estimates \hat{q} for some dataset, \mathcal{D}_E , not seen by \mathcal{M}_Q during training. The second step involves training another model, \mathcal{M}_E , using \mathcal{D}_E but where the target is the absolute error of the first model. To do this, the ground truth quality scores, q^* , are required, and the target for the model \mathcal{M}_E is then $\epsilon^* = |\hat{q} - q^*|$.

This method allows for epistemic uncertainty to be estimated directly by subtracting an estimate of the aleatoric uncertainty from the prediction (Lahlou et al., 2023).

G.1.7 Conformal Prediction

Conformal prediction can be combined with any pre-trained classification or regression model under the assumption that the data is IID (Shafer and Vovk, 2007). Given an error probability ϵ , the method has formal guarantees that the true value will be within the predictive uncertainty interval with probability at least $1 - \epsilon$.

The model is first trained on part of the labeled data and then used to make predictions for the remainder of the labeled data. These predictions are scored using a non-conformity measure, outputting a set of nonconformity scores α_i . In a regression setting, a common non-conformity measure is the absolute difference between the ground truth labels y_i and the predicted values \hat{y}_i :

$$\alpha_i = |\hat{y}_i - y_i| \quad (10)$$

From the set of nonconformity scores it is possible to compute the probability that a prediction deviates from the ground truth by an α_i amount. Conversely, it is possible to determine which non-conformity score α_i corresponds to the $1 - \epsilon$ percentile. This value is denoted α_s and it can be used to construct confidence intervals around new predictions without ground truth labels:

$$\Gamma_i^\epsilon = \hat{y}_i \pm \alpha_s \quad (11)$$

This produces the same uncertainty interval for all predictions. There is an optional normalization step, dividing the non-conformity score by σ_i , which estimates how difficult y_i is to predict. The parameter σ_i is usually estimated by a separate model trained for the task and it is also used when constructing the predictive interval: $\Gamma_i^\epsilon = \hat{y}_i \pm \alpha_s \sigma_i$.

In the context of MT evaluation, Zerva and Martins (2023) used other uncertainty estimation methods, such as Monte Carlo dropout, to compute σ_i .³² On the other hand, Giovannotti (2023) used the sum of distances between an observation and its k -nearest neighbours to estimate σ_i .

³²Specifically, for any method that estimates predictive uncertainty with a Gaussian, Zerva and Martins (2023) used the

G.2 Evaluation of Uncertainty-Aware Models

Two desirable features of [uncertainty-aware](#) translation evaluation systems were identified by [Glushkova et al. \(2021\)](#):

1. It should still be possible to use an uncertainty-aware system to make point predictions, and these should not be worse than a similar model without uncertainty.
2. The uncertainty estimate should reflect the failure probability of the system.

To this end, there are multiple approaches to evaluating the quality of an uncertainty-aware model. The first criteria can be evaluated using the Pearson correlation coefficient between the point predictions made from the uncertainty-aware model and the ground-truth scores, often referred to in the literature as the [predictive Pearson score \(PPS\)](#) to distinguish it from other correlations. Ideally, some benchmark correlation would be known to determine whether the uncertainty-aware model is performing at least as well as a similar model without uncertainty.

Another score, known as the [uncertainty Pearson score \(UPS\)](#) in the literature, is used to measure the correlation between the prediction errors and the uncertainty estimates.

Other evaluation techniques include:

- Negative log-likelihood
- Sharpness
- [Expected calibration error \(ECE\)](#) - see [Kuleshov et al. \(2018\)](#)

estimated standard deviation $\hat{\sigma}$ to compute the $1 - \epsilon$ Gaussian quantile and used that for σ_i . For example, for $\epsilon = 0.1$, i.e., a 90% confidence interval, $\sigma_i = 1.64 \times \hat{\sigma}$.

Appendix H Tools and Datasets

H.1 Quality Estimation Models and Frameworks

The following [QE](#) tools are available for use:

1. OpenKiwi (this implements the predictor-estimator architecture described in Section [E.1](#)): [GitHub](#)
2. COMET-QE (see Section [E.2.2](#)): [HuggingFace](#)
3. COMET-KIWI: [HuggingFace](#)
4. COMET-KIWI-XL: [HuggingFace](#)
5. COMET-KIWI-XXL: [HuggingFace](#)
6. NJUQE Framework (used by the [NJUNLP](#) submission to the QE shared task at [WMT 2022](#) and [2023](#)): [GitHub](#)

H.2 Annotated Datasets

These are datasets containing authentic data suitable for [QE](#) tasks; there may be overlap between datasets.

1. [MLQE-PE](#) dataset: [GitHub](#)
2. [WMT 2022 QE](#) data: [GitHub](#)
3. [WMT 2023 QE](#) data: [GitHub](#)
4. [WMT 2023](#) data from the metrics shared task: [Google Drive](#)
5. [WMT pre-2023 DA](#) data from the metrics shared task: [HuggingFace](#)
6. [WMT pre-2023 MQM](#) data from the metrics shared task: [HuggingFace](#)
7. [WMT pre-2023 SQM](#) data from the metrics shared task: [HuggingFace](#)
8. Google MQM data repository: [GitHub](#)
9. Unbabel data repository: [GitHub](#)

H.3 Challenge Datasets

1. [ACES](#) dataset: [HuggingFace](#)
2. [DEMETER](#) dataset: [GitHub](#)
3. [MT-TestSuite](#): [GitHub](#)

H.4 Critical Errors and Hallucinations Datasets

1. [WMT 2021 CED](#) data: [GitHub](#)
2. Subset of the original Unbabel annotations of the 2022 English-Russian [MQM](#) data: [GitHub](#)
3. [Guerreiro et al. \(2023b\)](#) hallucinations data : [GitHub](#)
4. [HalOmi](#) dataset: [GitHub](#)

H.5 Other

1. SMAUG framework: [GitHub](#)
2. Test-time adaptation (see [Zhan et al. \(2023\)](#) and Section 9.4): [GitHub](#)
3. GEMBA scoring script: [GitHub](#)

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